

Education and the Event: A Symposium

Introduction: Education and the Event

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While I am writing this introduction, there is a thunderstorm outside; lightning illuminates the almost black sky in irregular intervals. I'm waiting for the next lightning flash to come; I don't know when it will come, but I know it is coming. And even though I know there will be another flash of lightning, at times I give up waiting, my attention dissipates, but then there it is, in a sudden flash of light. I continue to write and can't help but thinking that this same anticipation, and loss of anticipation, happens in education, in teaching as well as in learning. Something happens (at times) outside the horizon of anticipation and expectation, and I learn; in the blink of an eye, I am given an insight into something difficult which suddenly becomes clear. In a flash of lightning, I know, I understand what I didn't understand before.

Are these two examples, the flash of lightning in a thunderstorm and the sudden realization or understanding of something I am set to learn, descriptions of what can be considered an event? Are they events? To genuinely address these questions, we must first of all ask what it means for something to be an event. This in order to come closer to an answer to what an educational event, an event in or of education, could be. A flash of lightning is always singular; just like the signature, it occurs as a singular event within a general system. As Jacques Derrida (2007) says in the conference talk published as "A Certain Impossible Possibility of Saying the Event," "[R]epetition must already be at work in the singularity of the event, and with the repetition, the erasure of the first occurrence is already underway" (p. 453). There is certainly repetition in the recurrence of lightning in a thunderstorm; lightning signs with its singular signature each time it strikes, it is recognizable, we know what to look for, we know how it looks, we know it when we see it, we know its general features, but still each time it is different, its singularity erased, as when we sign a formal document with our names. But the event, Derrida holds, must also be absolutely unexpected for it to be an event. Must it then, we might ask, occur as a bolt from the blue, as the idiom goes? This idiom is often misunderstood as describing a lightning bolt striking out of a clear sky, but the idiom, in fact, has its origin in ancient warfare, referring to a projectile fired from a crossbow. However, the idiom expresses, one could even say translates, the same sense of the unexpected as the Swedish idiom *en blix från klar himmel*, meaning a flash of lightning from a clear sky. But if we examine the two idioms carefully, it becomes clear that the translation is not precise enough, since in war the possibility of a bolt from the blue is indeed possible, just like a flash of lightning during a thunderstorm. A bolt from the blue, or a flash of lightning in a thunderstorm, is thus not an event, since "[p]recisely because it's possible," says Derrida, "[i]t merely develops and unfolds a possibility, a potentiality that is already present and therefore it is not an event" (p. 450). The event, similar but not identical to the Swedish idiom, must appear to be impossible; it must remain absolutely unanticipated and unexpected.

Let's visit another example. Take the notion of play, the game, as in a game of chess, a soccer or hockey game, in which we have to adhere to certain prescribed, agreed-upon rules, that is, what I called above a system of generality. Thus, each play, each game is different, singular, but still an event, albeit an event for which we indeed often have expectations. We know that it is coming, but we don't know, exactly, what form and shape it will take. The excitement in attending a game

is, precisely, that we know the rules, the statistics of each team and player, but we don't know how the game will be played out. We might expect a team or a player to win, but we can't be sure, because each game is singular, repeating itself within the prescribed rules of the game as something new and never before witnessed. But since there are prescribed rules that make the game possible, must we not, with Derrida, say that the game "merely develops and unfolds a possibility, a potentiality that is already present and therefore it is not an event"?

How about Schiller's theory of play? The "play impulse," as he calls it, "would aim at the extinction of time in time and the reconciliation of becoming with absolute being, of variation with identity" (14th Letter). But if, as Schiller would argue, time is the time of the game, and play is becoming, and the game itself is absolute being, an event in which we discern identity in variation and variation in identity, then play as an event (the reconciliation of becoming and absolute being) is the possibility of being (i.e., the limits of play are also its possibility and potential), which, as we have seen, disqualifies it as an event in Derrida's sense. So, if the event cannot be founded on rules and the consequences of the rules that would make an event possible (such as Hegelian dialectics, or Schiller's notion of play), then we must with Derrida imagine it as im-possible, meaning that the event cannot be inscribed within the binarism of the possible-impossible dichotomy. The event must come as a flash from a clear sky; the event is without foundation, causality, and reason. Can there be such an event in education, within an educational setting or the pedagogical situation, that is, an im-possible event? Is the im-possible at all possible in education? Can we learn the im-possible?

The event as im-possible, as François Raffoul explains in the first essay of the symposium section of this issue, must be thought as being without reason, exceeding reason, pure eventfulness. As he states, the event as im-possible is "that which happens outside the conditions of possibility offered in advance by a subject of representation, outside the transcendental conditions of possibility." Raffoul goes on in his essay to indicate how we can begin to or prepare for thinking the event in its im-possibility, which leads him to consider ethics and responsibility in relation to the event. Such a responsibility of the event he finds in Derrida's analysis of hospitality. Hospitality, Raffoul asserts, can only come about without invitation; the one who comes, the *arrivant*, does so without invitation, unanticipated and unexpected. The *arrivant* is the one who exceeds my power as host, the one I have not prepared to welcome or refuse. The *arrivant* crosses the limits of expectation by disrupting the regulated traditions of reception. The one who comes, in this sense, arrives without warning, beyond the power of rational or causal explanation.

Jean-Luc Marion (2015) refers to Charles Baudelaire's poem "A un passante" ("To a Passer-By") to exemplify the futility of explaining the event. Baudelaire's poem, Marion holds, stages an encounter with the unanticipated, free of causal or rational preconditions. As Marion has it, in Baudelaire's poem "an event happens by the simple fact that this woman passes and I cross her path without having the least cause to render a reason for her presence or for my own" (p. 183). A chance meeting, not even a meeting, since the woman doesn't even acknowledge the encounter; there is no reciprocal recognition that the encounter ever took place at all, but still, for the poet, it is an event, since it touched him by being, precisely, without cause or reason.

Another literary example, perhaps more closely related to hospitality, is the appearance of Leggatt in Joseph Conrad's (2007) short story "The Secret Sharer." The scene is the following: A captain

of a ship, new to his command, has unconventionally volunteered to take the first anchor watch. While pondering his isolation and unfamiliarity with the ship and his crew, he paces the deck and notices a rope side-ladder that has not been hauled in. He goes to correct the matter and haul the ladder in, but when he attempts to get the ladder over the railing, it does not budge. The captain, surprised, looks over the railing: "I saw at once something elongated and pale floating close to the ladder. Before I could form a guess a faint flash of phosphorescent light, which seemed to issue from the naked body of a man, flickered in the sleeping water with the elusive, silent play of summer lightning in a night sky" (p. 178). The appearance of Leggatt, the naked man in the water, arrives as a lightning flash, completely unexpectedly and seemingly without cause or reason. The captain, taken by surprise, is at a loss at what to do and how to act; "my first words were prompted by just that troubled incertitude. 'What's the matter?' I asked in my ordinary tone, speaking down to the face upturned exactly under mine. 'Cramp,' it answered, no louder" (p. 179). This slightly comical interaction in a sense puts the finger on the almost absurd situation when faced with an absolutely unanticipated event. Without knowing who the man in the water is at this point, the captain takes him in, not knowing the man's history or if he bears good or ill intentions. Yet the captain receives him and helps him aboard. We could say, then, that Leggatt's visitation, as an *arrivant*, exceeds the power of the captain as host; the captain has no rules or conventions to apply, other than welcoming the uninvited man in the water to join him on the ship. Leggatt's arrival carries with it the signs of a pure event. However, the captain's gesture of welcome also necessitates keeping Leggatt secret. But I will end my reflection on Conrad's story here before it leads too far into what a secret entails. Nevertheless, this literary encounter exemplifies, I would like to suggest, what Raffoul, with Derrida, considers the im-possibility of hospitality: that is, the very eventfulness of this absolutely unforeseen visitation. Hospitality and the ethics of hospitality can have significant implications for how we as educators approach our encounters with both students and other learners, and pedagogical content in itself. And Raffoul's essay provides a solid foundation for beginning to think the event and hospitality in terms of how they affect our educational practice.

James M. Magrini's contribution, "The Enigmatic Figure of Socrates in Heidegger: A Pure Vision of Education as Attuned Event of Learning," provides a thorough reading of Heidegger's Socrates and how the lighting of Being as event informs learning. Magrini centers his essay on the importance of how an original learning event creates wonder and amazement (*Erstaunen*), and how this is depicted and thought in Heidegger and Plato. Another focus of importance for learning as event in Magrini's essay is the notion of lighting. As Magrini states, connecting Heidegger's thinking with Plato's, "The lighting and enabling power of Being that Plato intimates in the *allegory* [of the cave] is the event and occurrence of 'lighting' within which Dasein participates when revealing and founding and grounding a world and appropriating a historical destiny." Thus Magrini underscores that, with Heidegger, the original event of learning as lighting, or clearing, is necessarily ontological, upsetting Plato's insistence of learning as an epistemological concern. This is, however, addressed by Heidegger through a confrontation (*Auseinandersetzung*) with Plato, by attending to the unsaid in Plato's thought. It is this confrontation, in the end, which gives rise to the amazement and wonder of the original event (*Ereignis*) of learning. It is the very performative act of Heidegger's reading of Plato, and by extension of Magrini's reading of Heidegger and Plato, that stages an event of learning, even beyond onto-theological Platonism and Heidegger's early thinking in *Being and Time*, and leads toward or on the way to another way of thinking, being, and learning.

Another confrontation takes place in Klas Roth's essay titled "A Free Flow Between Becomings and Becoming Imperceptible—Rare, but Possible." Roth's analysis centers on Gilles Deleuze's philosophy, and specifically on how Deleuze might, in fact, not be as positive about the future of humanity as is propounded by some posthumanist scholars. This, then, constitutes the confrontation in Roth's essay. But Roth's analysis of Deleuze should not only be seen as a critique of posthumanism, since it elucidates and contextualizes Deleuze's later thinking beyond its being a simple tool for Roth to deconstruct posthumanistic applications of Deleuze's philosophy. Roth's reading of Deleuze especially emphasizes his notions of becoming versus becoming imperceptible and active versus reactive forces, which Roth complicates (in a positive sense) to make them not be so easy and straight-forward as, for example, Rose Braidotti would have it when she exclusively focuses on the positive, active side of becoming. Conversely, Roth points out the inevitability of both reactive and active forces in our lives, and that there is always the possibility of a "pure event" which uncovers our singularity as beings (human and non-human). The importance for education that Roth highlights in his essay is, precisely, how we should cultivate a way of thinking that makes possible the development of becoming imperceptible. Such cultivation opens us up for the pure event of "singularization" which lets us, teachers and students, creatively reinvent ourselves, respond in an ethical way to reactive suppressive and repressive forces which hinder genuine thinking, learning, and development. The event of singularization as an educational event also creates lines of flight that can help us escape fixed and determined identities and stagnated ways of thinking, an escape which, in turn, lets us become other than what we are. What is more, these lines of flight, or disruptive events, imply new ways of learning as well as new ways of teaching. The educational event, thought in this way, reveals the heretofore unknown, that which appears only in a "fundamental encounter" with that which is yet unthought. This, Roth argues finally, is the real possibility and freedom: to balance the reactive and active, the destructive and the creative forces, which together let the singularization of the pure event be what we can become, is perhaps what a Deleuzian education would strive for.

Deleuze's thinking is also prominent in Ingrid Andersson's essay "The Relationship Between Common Sense and Thinking: Keeping with the Event in Education." In her essay, Andersson analyzes the two concepts "common sense" and "thinking" through the lens of the philosophies of Gilles Deleuze and Hannah Arendt. She positions herself by exploring how the two concepts' significance for education can be developed by reconciling the thinking of Deleuze and Arendt. The event in Andersson's essay is to be understood, in relation to the two concepts common sense and thinking, as a linguistic and an exterior phenomenon. As Andersson makes clear in her reading of Deleuze, the event can be expressed through language but not captured in language, making the event exterior to linguistic expression. In other words, there is a significance inherent in the eventfulness of the event which cannot be reduced to signs; that is, the event must be translated to be known, and so turned into knowledge, but what is lost in translation is, precisely, the eventfulness of the event. In her reading of Arendt, Andersson relates to Deleuze's contention of the event as trace by pointing out how for Arendt to imagine the event, it must be known, meaning already past, and so possible to represent as a significant event. It is only in this way, Arendt suggests, that we can judge an event justly. The judge of an event must be a witness to what has happened. And as Andersson succinctly states, "Thinking is always an afterthought; it comes *after the event.*" This *Nachträglichkeit*, to borrow a word from Freud, gives us, paradoxically, the promise of another thought yet to come. And it is in creation, creation without past, that we *become*; or, as Andersson has it, "[F]or both Arendt and Deleuze the main question is not what we

can know *but what we can become.*” This, to paraphrase Andersson, is the futural possibility of education.

In the final essay in the symposium, Andrew Gibbons introduces a notion of the event which is perhaps at the very heart of the event and eventfulness, namely love. Can we ever be sure of an other’s love? Most of us know that, in the past, someone has loved us and said, “Yes, I love you.” But can we be sure? What knowledge is there to rely on? When do I know that there is love? Mutual love? There is always that event horizon that swallows my knowing and erases my certainty. Gibbons approaches the notion of love from the perspective of the film *Interstellar*, directed by Christopher Nolan, and, importantly, juxtaposes it with programmatic statements on the development and improvement of education, the bureaucratic promises of monetary and material support, often political, of people in charge of education. In *Interstellar*, as Gibbons shows, we encounter the clash between science and love, and the intricate question of which of the two, in the end, can save humanity (if this is possible).

So what, then, can the movie *Interstellar* teach us about love? And about the event of love in education? As an early childhood educator, Gibbons asks the important question of whether we can measure, scientifically, a child’s progress and development. And even if we can, should we? What *Interstellar* suggests, according to Gibbons, is that it is only as an event that love can be learned, that is, as “pure finding,” as Heidegger has it. In other words, love as an event that cannot be known and that so is impossible to measure and assess. The paradox, then, is that we need both science and love, but as Gibbons makes abundantly clear, love has been afforded neither time nor space enough in education today.

These five essays, all concerned with the event and with the event as an educational phenomenon, make clear that there is another side to education than the insistence on the instrumental and scientific drive for accountability, which is the bureaucratic word for ethics. That other side, that other dimension, is a line of flight or escape, that fleeting idea of love, which refuses to be pinned down and determined by methods of assessment, learning outcomes and criteria, rubrics, and other instruments to objectify knowledge, which politicians are so eager to implement in order to gain votes and approval. What the essays in the symposium show is the importance of that which is unsaid, the inexpressible, in any representation of knowledge. Taken together, the symposium essays show the paradoxical necessity of translating into words the very eventfulness of the event in education, an eventfulness which can only strike like lightning from a clear sky.

References

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Thinking the Event

François Raffoul

Introduction

In the pages that follow, I will attempt to identify several features of the event which I explored in my recent book, *Thinking the Event* (2020). In this work, I have attempted a philosophical inquiry into what constitutes an event as an event, its very eventfulness: not *what* happens, not *why* it happens, but *that* it happens, and what “happening” mean: not the *eventum*, what has happened, but the *evenire*, the sheer happening of what happens. By the expression “thinking the event,” I do not mean the appropriation by thought of the event, under the authority of the principle of reason. Rather, “thinking the event” means to give thought to its very *eventfulness*, its sheer happening, which I suggest necessarily exceeds both reason and subjectivity. Indeed, one could say that the event, in its disruptive and unpredictable happening, *exceeds* both the concept and the anticipation of a subject. Such a project goes against the tradition that has always neutralized the event by anchoring it in a reason or a cause. Indeed, the concept of event has traditionally been understood and neutralized within a metaphysics of causality, subjectivity, and reason, in a word, subjected to the demands of rational thought. An event is interpreted either as the accident of a substrate or substance, as the effect or deed of a subject or an agent, or else it is ordered and organized according to causality, when it is not included within fate or a rational order. In all instances, it answers to the demands of the principle of sufficient reason, which states that no event happens without a cause or a reason. In the words of Leibniz (Leibniz and Clarke, 2000), the “great” principle of natural philosophy and key metaphysical principle of truth is “the *principle of sufficient reason*, namely, that nothing happens without a reason why it should be so rather than otherwise” (p. 7). Such reason can also be a cause, as the principle of sufficient reason merges with a “principle of causality,” which states that every event is caused to be the event that it is. Again, in Leibniz’s (Leibniz and Clarke, 2000) words: “Nothing is without reason, or no effect is without a cause” (Leibniz, cited in Heidegger [1991], p. 21).

However, as Heidegger (1991) demonstrates in his 1955-1956 lecture course *The Principle of Reason*, the principle of reason self-deconstructs, because it cannot apply to itself its own requirements without undermining itself: if the principle of reason states that everything that happens must have a reason, then what is the reason for the principle of reason? Does the principle of reason have a reason? “*Nihil est sine ratione*. Nothing is without reason, says the principle of reason. Nothing—which means not even this principle of reason, certainly it least of all. It may then be that the principle of reason, that whereof it speaks, and this speaking itself do not belong within the jurisdiction of the principle of reason. To think this remains a grave burden. In short it means that *the principle of reason is without reason*. Said still more clearly: ‘Nothing without reason’— *this, which is something, is without reason*” (p. 17; emphasis mine). One divines here how the principle of reason is caught in a circle (What is the reason of the principle of reason? What is the foundation of a foundation?) that throws it into an abyss, into the abyss of its own impossible foundation.

Indeed, in order to be a ground, the ground must itself be without foundation and therefore groundless! This led Gilles Deleuze (cited in Zourabichvili [2012]) to speak of the paradoxical nature of the logic of grounding, of the “comical ungrounding” of the principle of reason: “But who still speaks of a foundation, when the logic of grounding or the principle of reason leads precisely to its own ‘ungrounding,’ comical and disappointing” (p. 57). The principle of reason collapses (“runs aground”) at the very place of its impossible foundation, “there where,” as Derrida (2005b) puts it in *Rogues*, “the *Grund* opens up onto the *Abgrund*, where giving reasons [*rendre-raison*] and giving an account [*rendre-compte*]*—logon didonai* or *principium reddendae rationis**—*are threatened by or drawn into the abyss” (p. 122). The question “why,” the question seeking reasons, opens onto an abyss. As Heidegger (1991) argued, “Whenever we pursue the ground/reason of a being, we ask: why? Cognition stalks this interrogative word from one reason to another. The ‘why’ allows no rest, offers no stop, *gives no support*” (p. 126; my emphasis). The question ‘why,’ seeking a foundation, in fact undermines it. Reason is without reason, leading Derrida (2005) to ask: “The value of reason, the desire for reason, the dignity of reason—are these rational? Do these have to do wholly with reason?” (p. 120).

The Transcendental, the Event

Reason is thus exceeded from within, opening onto pure eventfulness, itself happening outside reason. In fact, each time unpredictable and incalculable, an event always exceeds or “suspends” (Marion, 2002a, p. 160) the principle of sufficient reason. As such, the event constitutes a challenge to reason and understanding. As Derrida (Derrida and Roudinesco [2004]), puts it, “The event is what comes and, in coming, comes to surprise me, to surprise and to suspend comprehension: the event is first of all *that which* I do not first of all comprehend. Better, the event is first of all *that* I do not comprehend. The fact that I do not comprehend: my incomprehension” (p. 50). This is why for Derrida it is not a matter of complying with the demands of the principle of reason, but instead of not “denying or ignoring this unforeseeable and incalculable coming of the other” (Derrida and Roudinesco [2004], p. 50). It is a matter of freeing eventfulness from the demands of the principle of reason. No longer placed under the authority of the principle of sufficient reason, the event must be rethought as the incalculable and unpredictable arrival of what will always remain other—and thus inappropriable—for the one to whom it happens. In that sense, the event also comes as an excess in relation to the subject, and can only “naturally take by surprise not only the addressee but also the subject to whom and by whom it is supposed to happen” (Derrida [2004], p. 60). It would then be a matter, in order to give thought to the event in its eventfulness, of freeing the event from the demands of the principle of sufficient reason, as well as from the predominance of transcendental modes of thought, which claim to provide prior conditions of possibility for the occurrence of events. Indeed, it may well be the case that events are precisely eventful when not pre-organized or prepared by some transcendental conditions, or anticipated by a transcendental subject, when they break or “pierce” the horizon provided by transcendental conditions. An event cannot be made possible by a prior condition, or rather, as Jean-Luc Nancy (2007) pointed out, it “must not be the object of a programmatic and certain calculation.... It must be the possibility of the impossible (according to a logic used often by Derrida), it must know itself as such, that is to say, know that it happens also in the incalculable and the unassignable” (p. 49). An event cannot be reduced to what *can* happen: it does not happen because it can happen, but rather happens without being made possible in advance and to that extent can be called “impossible,” Jean-Luc Marion (2015) going so far as to state that the event

can only be impossible, the impossible itself: “Moreover, [the event] always appears to us at bottom as impossible, or even as the impossible, since it does not belong to the domain of the possible, of that of which we are able” (p. 182). The impossible, in this context, does not mean what cannot be or happen. Rather, the impossible, or the im-possible, as Derrida writes it, means that which happens outside the conditions of possibility offered in advance by a subject of representation, outside the transcendental conditions of possibility. Thinking the event will require to break with a certain transcendental mode of thinking, as the event deconstructs the transcendental as such.

The event deconstructs the transcendental, the transcendental conditions of possibility, the “power” of the possible. In *Paper Machine*, Derrida (2005a) resituates his relation to the motif of the transcendental and to the expression “quasi-transcendental,” as discussed by Rodolphe Gasché: “it is definitely not by chance that the modality of quasi (or the logical-rhetorical fiction of as if) has so often imposed itself on me to make a word into a phrase, and first of all, especially—it has often been noted and commented on—around the word transcendental” (p. 83). At stake is a questioning of the tradition of the transcendental, of the very motif of the conditions of possibility. “A question of problematic context and strategies, presumably: one must in this place relentlessly reaffirm questions of the transcendental type; and in that place, almost simultaneously, also ask questions about the history and the limits of what is called ‘transcendental’” (Derrida [2005a], p. 83). Derrida does not simply want to do away with transcendental strategies (he is quite clear on this point), he instead seeks to question the transcendental and reorient it toward the “quasi,” the “impossible,” and the event: “For nothing can discredit the right to the transcendental or ontological question. This is the only force that resists empiricism and relativism. Despite appearances to which philosophers in a hurry often rush, nothing is less empiricist or relativist than a certain attention to the multiplicity of contexts and the discursive strategies they govern; than a certain insistence on the fact that a context is always open and nonsaturable; or than taking into account the perhaps and the quasi in thinking about the event” (Derrida [2005a], p. 92). Mentioning the transcendental “condition of possibility” “in all its forms: medieval onto-theology, criticism, or phenomenology” (Derrida [2005a], p. 92), Derrida shows that at issue is the traditional demand for conditions of possibility, that is, for a ground. In question is “the philosophical inheritance, namely the demand for the condition of possibility (the a priori, the originary, or ground, all different forms of the same radical demand and of any philosophical ‘question’)” (Derrida [2005a], p. 84). The critique of the notion of conditions of possibility includes a critique, in fine, of the motif of ground and foundation, Derrida explaining, “What is thus said of the condition of possibility also goes, by analogy, for the ‘ground,’ the ‘origin,’ the ‘root’ of ‘radicality,’ and so on” (Derrida [2005a], p. 84).

The absence of ground, as noted prior, reveals the site of the event, which is now also tied to the impossible, which Derrida (2005b) writes as im-possible: im-possible, “that is, when it is not programmed by a structure of expectation and anticipation that annuls it by making it possible and thus foreseeable” (p. 128). Therein lies Derrida’s thought of the impossible, which designates that which happens outside of the anticipating conditions of possibility of the egological subject, outside of the horizons of expectation proposed by the subject, outside of transcendental horizons of calculability. The issue is to free “the pure eventfulness of the event” (Derrida, 2003, p. 134) by breaking the power of the ego and its attempts to neutralize it. To the power of the subject as neutralization of the event, Derrida will oppose “the im-possible” as paradoxical possibility of the

event. To the whole machination of the subject, to the establishment of the power of someone, some “I can,” “to all this,” Derrida (2003) writes, “I would oppose, in the first place, everything I placed earlier under the title of the im-possible, of what must remain (in a non-negative fashion) foreign to the order of my possibilities, to the order of the ‘I can’” (p. 134). Derrida engages a deconstruction of this tradition, reversing the conditions of possibility into conditions of impossibility! It is indeed a matter of converting the possible into the impossible and recognizing that what happens arises out of the impossible. It is when “the impossible makes itself possible” that “the event takes place” as the possibility of the impossible (p. 90). It is the impossible that is possible, that happens. For Derrida (2005a), for an event to be possible, it must arise from the im-possible (it must happen as the im-possible), and not be made possible by prior conditions. In fact, it can only be an event by breaking the possible. “That, indisputably, is the paradoxical form of the event: if an event is only possible, in the classic sense of this word, if it fits in with conditions of possibility, if it only makes explicit, unveils, reveals, or accomplishes that which was already possible, then it is no longer an event. For an event to take place, for it to be possible, it has to be, as event, as invention, the coming of the impossible” (p. 90). Indeed, to make an event possible in advance is to render it impossible as an event, if it is the case that an event interrupts horizons of possibilities. It is paradoxically the condition of possibility that impossibilizes the experience of which it claims to be the condition; it is on the contrary the im-possible, as leap outside of the horizon of expectations, which possibilizes the event, the eventfulness of the event, what Derrida (2005a) calls the happening/arrival of the *arrivant* (*l’arrivée de l’arrivant*). Everything takes place as if the impossible is what truly enabled or possibilized the possible and as if the possible could only be possible as impossible. The possible “‘is’ the impossible” (Derrida, 2005a, p. 79), and in turn, the impossible is the true condition of possibility, Derrida going so far in *Rogues* (2005b) as writing of the impossible “as the only possibility and as the condition of possibility” (p. 47). The old expression of “condition of possibility” should be understood as “condition of impossibility,” undecidedly possible and impossible, possible as impossible, Derrida (2005b) often combining the two in one segment, as in “conditions of possibility or/and impossibility” (for instance, p. 49). He explains in *Paper Machine* (2005a): “As I try to show elsewhere more concretely, less formally but with more logical sequence, that requires us to think the possible . . . as the impossible.” Now, if “the possible ‘is’ the im-possible here,” then, Derrida (2005a) continues, “the ‘condition of possibility’ is a ‘condition of impossibility’” (p. 79). That thought of the event as happening from the impossible, he concludes, “has always guided me, between the possible and the impossible. This is what has so often prompted me to speak of a condition of impossibility” (Derrida, 2005a, p. 90).

Event and Cause

The deconstruction of the transcendental implies the renouncing of the reference to ground when thinking the event. Another conception of the event is called for, one no longer anchored in a cause-substrate, but happening *without ground*. With respect to causality, instead of the event following the cause, one might suggest that the event is the original phenomenon. Events do not simply follow pre-determined sequences. An event “worthy of the name” represents the surge of the new through which it precisely does not “follow” from a previous cause. A new understanding of temporality is here required: not a ruled sequence coming from the past to the present, but an eventful temporality, coming from the future, disrupting the causal networks, and transforming the entire complex of temporality, indeed transforming the past itself and our relationship to it.

Nietzsche describes an “inversion of temporality,” an *Umkehrung der Zeit*, in the process of an *a posteriori* imputation of a cause to an event. Nietzsche calls this phenomenon the error of “false causality,” which lies in the retroactive assigning of a cause to an event, an after-the-fact (re)construction that is then posited as having existed *before* the event. “I’ll begin with dreams: a particular sensation, for instance, a sensation due to a distant cannon shot, has a cause imputed to it (*untergeschoben*) afterwards (*nachträglich*).” (Nietzsche, 1997, pp, 32-33). Once the cause has been introduced, *after the event*, then, it is then said to exist prior to the event, an event that has now been transformed into necessity and meaning, a meaning that we have introduced: “In the meantime, the sensation persists in a kind of resonance: it waits, as it were, until the drive to find causes allows it to come into the foreground—not as an accident anymore, but as ‘meaning’” (p. 33). As Nietzsche explains, the sensation then becomes part of “a whole little novel in which precisely the dreamer is the protagonist.” Everyone knows the experience in a dream when the dreamer hears a sound which then becomes included in the narrative in a causal way. What was first a sheer event, perceived outside any causal network, is then integrated in the dream and reconstructed as causal origin in the narration. The event has been reconstructed and is now said to be happening *according to causality*. Of course, the cause was produced *after the fact*, and then re-injected as that from which the event occurred. “The cannon shot shows up in a *causal* way, and time seems to flow backward” (p. 33).

In fact, one must invert this inversion, and posit that the event happens *before* the cause. Only after something has happened can one begin to account for it causally. That something happens is the original fact. In that sense, there is nothing before the event. This is why Claude Romano (2009) states, in *Event and World*, “Pure beginning from nothing, an event, in its an-archic bursting forth, is absolved from all antecedent causality” (p. 41), or further: “An event has no cause, because *it is its own origin*” (p. 42).¹ It is traditionally admitted that events are determined by prior causes, and Kant (1998) insisted that “everything *that happens* presupposes a previous state, upon which it follows without exception according to a rule” (p. 484). But are we to think that events simply follow pre-determined sequences? And if this was the case, would they still be events in the proper sense? By introducing the new in the world, indeed by bringing forth a new world, does an event not disqualify prior causal contexts and networks? To that extent, an event could not be “explained” by prior events because its occurrence has transformed the very context in which it happens. Jean-Luc Marion (2002) writes: “Inasmuch as it is a given phenomenon, the event does not have an adequate cause and cannot have one. Only in this way can it advance on the wings of a dove: unforeseen, unusual, unexpected, unheard of, and unseen” (p. 167). If “innerworldly facts” can indeed be causally explained, events in the proper sense exceed causal orders. “An event is marked off from all prior facts by its very arising—coming about from itself, free of any horizon of meaning and any prior condition. An event advenes only on its own horizon. It is a pure bursting forth from and in itself, unforeseeable in its radical novelty, and retrospectively establishing a rupture with the entire past...” (Romano, 2009, p. 42).² The event happens first. The cause is added after the fact. “In summa: an event is neither effected nor does it effect. Causa

¹ In Jean-Luc Marion’s (2002) words, the event *cannot* have a cause: “Now, it happens that the event—precisely because it arises in an unpredictable landing—overcomes measure and the understanding, and therefore is excepted from all adequate cause” (p. 167).

² As Marion (2002) also explains in *Being Given*, “In taking the event as the product of a cause, one confuses it with a simple fact, added afterwards to others” (p. 165).

is a capacity to produce effects that has been super-added to the events” (Nietzsche, 1968, p. 296). There are no causes: the cause is added after the fact as an interpretation (Nietzsche [1968] speaks of an “interpretation by causality” as a “deception” [p. 296]) insofar as it is sought. The law of causality “has been projected by us into every event.”

The Event as Pure Fact

The event is a fact, an encounter, occurring outside reason. No reasons will ever measure up to the happening of the event. The event of an encounter, for instance, is not subject to the principle of sufficient reason: “An encounter is always inexplicable,” writes Gilles Deleuze (cited in Zourabichvili [2012], p. 57). To think the event is to think such absolute inexplicability and contingency. The well-known paradigm of such an encounter outside of reason is the case of friendship, such as that described by Michel de Montaigne (1958) between him and Étienne de La Boétie. “If you press me to tell why I loved him, I feel that this cannot be expressed except by answering: because it was he; because it was I [*Si on me presse de dire pourquoi je l'aimais, je sens que cela ne se peut exprimer qu'en répondant: parce que c'était lui; parce que c'était moi*]” (p. 139). As Marion (2002) comments, the event of this friendship occurs “all at once, without warning or anticipation, according to an *arrival* without expectation and without rhythm” (p. 37). The event of friendship is a fact (it “imposes itself”), a fact and a chance irreducible to reason. Therefore, no reasons will ever measure up to the fact of the encounter, to the chance happening of friendship. As Derrida (1997) puts it in *The Politics of Friendship*, “The analysis of conditions of possibility, even existential ones, will never suffice in giving an account of the act or the event. An analysis of that kind will never measure up to what takes place, the effectivity—actuality—of what comes to pass—for example, a friendship which will never be reduced to the desire or the potentiality of friendship” (p. 17). Now the notion that philosophy is born out of an event that it does not control is “a shock to reason” in its quest for ultimate foundations. For “how is it supposed to find a foundation [*assise*] in that which defeats it, in the inexplicable or the aleatory?” In the end, what transpires is that “We cannot give the reason for an event” (Zourabichvili [2012], p. 57). As Heidegger (1991) stated, “The rose is without why.... [It] ‘blooms, because it blooms’” (p. 56-57). For Heidegger, that tautology, far from saying nothing, says everything, that is, the entire *eventful facticity* of the being: it happens *because* it happens. The *because* supersedes the *why*. The event becomes the highest reason. The reason given is harbored entirely within the fact of the being, that is, within the being itself, “the fact of its being a rose or its rose-being [*ihr Rose-sein*]” (Heidegger [1991], p. 57; *Der Satz vom Grund*, GA 10, p. 84, trans. slightly modified). Jean-Luc Nancy (2007) stressed that the world, not grounded on any principle, is a *fact*; it is only a fact (even if it is a singular fact, not being itself a fact within the world). It is not founded in reason or in God. It is the fact of a “mystery,” the mystery of an accidental, errant, or wandering existence. The world is neither necessary nor contingent, if contingency is defined in relation to necessity. Rather, it would be beyond or before necessity and of contingency, an *absolute fact*. It is possible to consider this facticity of the world “without referring it to a cause (neither efficient nor final)” (p. 45). The world is a fact without cause and without reason, it is “a fact without reason or end, and it is our fact” (p. 45). We are called, in this thought of the event of the world, to take on this facticity without reason of the world, as well as its non-sense, or rather the fact that its sense only lies in such a fact: “To think it, is to think this factuality, which implies not referring it to a meaning capable of appropriating it, but to placing in it, in its truth as a fact, all possible meaning” (p. 45). The world is a significance without a foundation in reason. The world as event is without reason

and is to itself its entire possible reason.

The Impersonality of the Event

One of the constitutive errors of the metaphysical tradition is its reliance on causality, its imposition of causes on every existence, on every event, as their *substratum*: causality is the alleged substrate of the event. “Being is thought into things everywhere as a cause, is *imputed* to things” (Nietzsche [1997], p. 20). We have *created* a world of causes, a world of wills, and a world of spirits. All happening is considered a doing, all doing is supposed to be the effect of a will; the world is understood as a multiplicity of doers; a doer or subject “was imputed to everything that happened” (Nietzsche [1997], p. 32). The belief in causality thus involves the belief in the subject. Yet Nietzsche (1967) insists that one cannot attach a doer to deeds, that “there is no ‘being’ behind doing, effecting, becoming,” that the doer “is merely a fiction added to the deed” (p. 24). The notion of an underlying subjectivity is contrary to the facts, an unphenomenological construction. Instead of immediate certainties, we have the following questions: “From where do I get the concept of thinking? Why do I believe in cause and effect? What gives me the right to speak of an ego, and even of an ego as cause, and finally of an ego as the cause of thought?” (Nietzsche [1989] p. 24). All these are constructs for Nietzsche, which he understands in terms of the constitutive role of language in thinking (our thinking relies and depends on our grammar). The subject thus appears as a linguistic construct. Indeed, an underlying substantial ego is not a phenomenological fact, but a metaphysical idol, and ultimately for Nietzsche a *linguistic* prejudice. The substantialist egology of the Cartesian tradition harbors an implicit metaphysics of grammar. “One infers here according to the grammatical habit: ‘thinking is an activity; every activity requires an agent; consequently—’” (p. 24). Metaphysical idols are nothing but grammatical structures: “formerly, one believed in the soul as one believed in grammar and the grammatical subject” (p. 67). The difference between a doer and the deed, i.e., the position of an agent or subject beneath the event, is made possible by a “seduction of language” that distinguishes an agent from its deed. There is no doer, only the deed.

There is no doer. This reveals the radical *impersonality* of the event, of any event: *it* happens, of itself. This impersonality here revealed (“there is” thinking) leads us to consider subjectless sentences such as “it rains.” If the event has no subject underlying it, whether as a cause or substrate, then the danger is to substantify the “it” in such expressions, as if it designated some substrate distinct from the happening. Just as the “popular mind,” Nietzsche (1967) tells us, distinguishes the lightning from its flash, just as it reifies the “it” in the “it rains,” just as it conceives of the event as an action requiring a subject (as if behind the manifestation of strength, there was an indifferent substratum that would have the freedom to be manifest strength or not), just as it “doubles the deed” (“it posits the same event first as cause and then a second time as its effect” (p. 45), the metaphysician distinguishes a subject from its effects. In fact, Nietzsche (1967) proclaims forcefully: “there is no such substratum; there is no ‘being’ behind doing, effecting, becoming; the doer is merely a fiction added to the deed—the deed is everything” (p. 45). “The deed is everything”; this expression would require and call for another conception of the event, in which such event would no longer be anchored in a cause-substrate, but happening from itself (and yet, as we will see, happening to someone). “If I say: ‘Lightning flashes,’ I have posited the flashing once as activity and once as subject, and have thus added on to the event (*Geschehen*) a being that is not identical with the event but that *remains, is, and does not ‘become’ (nicht wird)*).

To posit the event as effecting (Wirken), and effect (Wirkung) as being: that is the twofold error, or interpretation, of which we are guilty” (Nietzsche [2003], pp. 75-76).

The event rests on no substrate, has no author; this is why it is always impersonal: *it* happens. What of this “it”? Reflecting on the impersonality of the expression *es gibt* (“it gives, “there is”) in *On Time and Being*, Heidegger (1972) notes that the risk when discussing this “it” is to posit some “indeterminate power” that somehow would cause the event (p. 16). Here again, the problem resides in the very structure of language, in a certain grammar that divides subject and predicate, and determines the “it” as a separate entity with an efficiency of its own, leading to the belief in a metaphysical substrate. As such, this grammatical structure neutralizes the eventfulness of the event. It is a matter of no longer isolating the “it” from the happening of the event. The “it” does not refer to a subject existing under the event of being, but is co-extensive with such event. If I say “it rains,” the “it” designates the *raining* itself, i.e., the *event* of raining. The “it” does not designate an underlying substrate, but designates the impersonal eventfulness of the event itself. The “it” is a stand-in for no one.

The Performative, the Letting

The event is a radically impersonal phenomenon, enacted by no one, no subject, no self: the event thus occurs *outside the subject*. As Derrida (2004) states, an event is “something that happens in some sense without or before any subject, without or before anyone’s decision” (p. 10). The event exceeds the capacity of a subject, the power of a self. This is why Derrida (2004) ultimately rejected the notion of the performative to think the event, as it still relies too heavily on the action of a subject. One often associates the performative with the enacting of an event. “We traditionally say that the performative produces events—I do what I say, I open the session if I am presiding over it, I produce the event of which I speak. In general, we thus relate the possibility of the event that is produced to a performative initiative and thus to a performative responsibility” (p. 67). However, in such a performative, the event is neutralized by the position of a powerful subject. “A performative produces an event only by securing for itself, in the first-person singular or plural, in the present, and with the guarantee offered by conventions or legitimated fictions, the power that an ipseity gives itself to produce the event of which it speaks” (Derrida [2005b], p. 152). Just like so-called “constative” or theoretical language, the performative also misses the eventful in the event. “Now, just like the constative, it seems to me, the performative cannot avoid neutralizing, indeed annulling, the eventfulness of the event it is supposed to produce” (p. 152). Certainly, Derrida (2004) concedes, something does happen with the performative, but what is eventful exceeds it: “I am not saying that nothing then happens, but what happens is programmable, foreseeable, controlled, conditioned by conventions.” Therefore, “It can thus be said, I would dare say, that an event worthy of its name is an event that derails all performativity” (p. 67). This means that it is a matter of thinking the event outside of a problematic of power, “beyond all performative mastery, beyond all power” (Derrida [2005a], p. 94), as the event undoes both will and power. An event is not a power, but what Derrida calls a “weak” or “vulnerable” force. The experience of the event “defeats my will,” writes Derrida (2007). This is why when it comes to the event, it will not be a matter of doing (involving a will and a subject), but rather of a *letting*. As Derrida (2004) writes, when it comes to the event, it is a matter of abandoning the will and *letting* the event happen, as opposed to *making* it happen (a “making happen” that always mobilizes the power and will of a subject). “Must there not be an absence of the will to abandon, whence the question of letting-

happen rather than making-happen?" (p. 92).

Indeed, once the event is no longer referred to the demands of the principle of reason, no longer anchored in a subject-cause, it becomes possible to *let* it give itself in its eventfulness, in the way it happens each time. "Thinking the event" would here mean, not subjecting it to reason, but *letting it be*. "Thinking" here should be approached as a kind of letting, letting-be or *Gelassenheit* (Heidegger [2010], p. 71). Thinking the event would mean: letting the event happen of itself, an event which itself is a kind of letting. Letting the letting be, as it were. Indeed, "letting" is for Heidegger (as it is for Derrida, as we saw above) the "deepest meaning of being" (Heidegger [2003], p.59). For an event happens *of itself*, so that an event is never prepared, produced or made, but precisely let be. To the letting of the event of being corresponds the fundamental disposition of thinking as *Gelassenheit*, as letting-be. "Thinking the event" would mean here: letting ... the letting, letting the letting be.

As the event happens *of itself*, it undoes the power of a subject, placing us, as it were, no longer in the position of actors, but, as Jean-Luc Marion (2002a) suggests, of *witnesses*. As he clarifies, the term witness signifies the undoing of the transcendental subject constituting the event as object: "With the name witness, we must understand a subjectivity stripped of the characteristics that gave it transcendental rank" (p. 217). To the constituting subject, "there follows the witness—the constituted witness" (p. 216). The event happens of itself, not constituted by a transcendental subject. The event, Marion writes, essentially is a passing; it passes and passes of itself: *Il passe et se passe*, it passes and happens of itself. Let us stress here the capital importance of the motif of passing in the thinking of the event. The event essentially *passes*. The event belongs to the fundamental category of *passing*; not "being" in the sense of a substantial presence, but *passing*. As Marion (2015) explains, "First, it is not self-evident that in order to be, a being must subsist in permanence: indeed, what is proper to the event, by definition, is not to be insofar as it subsists in permanence, but insofar *as it passes*" (p. 89; my emphasis). The event passes [*passe*] and passes of itself [*se passe*], while exceeding us from all sides. This passing passes us by. Marion writes: "The phenomenon of the passing reached me and, so to speak, constituted me as not constituting it—to the point that all I have to do is recognize myself as the mere witness (the one who certainly saw what he has seen, but does not understand what he has seen), and I renounce my claim to be its transcendental subject" (p. 186). Hence, in Waterloo, the battle "passes and passes away on its own, without anybody making it or deciding it. It passes, and each watches it pass, fade into the distance, and then disappear, disappear like it had come—that is to say, of itself" (Marion [2002a, p. 228). We, as subjects of the event, are also passing, passing and bypassed (expropriated) in the passing of the event.

The event happens of itself, is impersonal, and yet it always happens to someone, bringing forth an eventful self, that is to say, a self that is constituted (but also undone) by the event. Heidegger shows how being is an event (*Ereignis*) in which we have a part as human beings. The human being is not the *ego cogito* of the Cartesian tradition in a position of subject, but the one who is concerned by the event of being and happening from it. This new perspective requires that the self, far from designating some substantial ego or pre-given I, itself must be understood as arising from an event. In that sense, the self as such *is* an event, coming to be as a response to the eventfulness of being. It will be necessary, in our understanding of the event, to think together the impersonality of the event with the arising and responding of a self, as if the *es gibt* was the site of

an “I” to be, as called for a self that is corresponding with an otherwise im-personal phenomenon. In this respect, one ought not to be too quick to set apart the impersonality of the event with the selfhood that is engaged by it. The event is impersonal, happens of itself, but engages a self which consists precisely in the reception of such event, in which the I suffers the “shock” and trauma of the event. What is at stake here in the task of thinking the event is to reveal how the self itself is an event, happening, as it were, in and from the happening of being. The self cannot be presupposed as a pre-given or pre-constituted subject but rather originates *in and as an event*.

Conclusion: The Ethics of the Event

Ultimately, it is a matter of being hospitable to the event, of letting it come and letting it happen as it happens. The happening of the event is the coming of an *arrivant*, an arrival that is welcomed by an original hospitality. Indeed, the ethics of the event, as I approach it here, is to be taken as an ethics of hospitality, a welcome of the event in its irruptive coming. Let us focus, in closing, on this original ethics of the event. Derrida recognized in a 2004 interview with *l’Humanité* the growing importance that the thinking of the event has taken for him, significantly insisting on its ethical scope: “what you say about a privileged attention to the event is correct. It has become more and more insistent. The event, as that which happens (*arrive*) unpredictably, singularly. Not only what happens, but also who happens/arrives, the *arrivant*. The question ‘what is to be done with what/who arrives?’ commands a thinking of hospitality, of the gift, of forgiveness, of the secret, of witnessing” (Derrida and Nielsberg [2004]; my translation). We see here emerge the thematics of a hospitality to the event, an ethical welcome of the event. Such hospitality is on the side of the *arrivant*, who comes whenever it comes. Hence Derrida’s distinction between invitation and visitation. Derrida (2007) explains: “The absolute arrivant must not be merely an invited guest, someone I’m prepared to welcome, whom I have the ability to welcome. It must be someone whose unexpected, unforeseeable arrival, whose *visitation—and here I’m opposing visitation to invitation—is such an irruption that I’m not prepared to receive the person. I must not even be prepared to receive the person, for there to be genuine hospitality*” (p, 451). Invitation is the expecting of some guest, without surprise. But hospitality requires “absolute surprise”: “I must be unprepared, or prepared to be unprepared, for the unexpected arrival of any other,” and he adds: “The other, like the Messiah, must arrive whenever he or she wants” (Derrida [1999], p. 70). This, indeed, is the very definition of the event, which Derrida (2003) captures in its most limpid simplicity in this passage: “Whatever happens, happens, whoever comes, comes (*ce qui arrive arrive*), and that, in the end, is the only event worthy of this name” (p. 129).

Hospitality, then, is a receiving or welcoming that has no power over its own welcoming, it is an opening without horizon, without horizon of expectation. The event is an unforeseeable happening, affecting a vulnerable subjectivity. “If an event worthy of this name is to arrive or happen, it must, beyond all mastery, affect a passivity. It must touch an exposed vulnerability, one without absolute immunity, without indemnity; it must touch this vulnerability in its finitude and in a nonhorizontal fashion, there where it is not yet or is already no longer possible to face or face up to the unforeseeability of the other” (Derrida [2005b], p. 152). It is to this extent that Derrida understands hospitality in its full sense as unconditional. It is unconditional because it arises out of the event of the other and not from some *conditions* laid out by a subject-host. The subject is powerless before the coming of the event as *arrivant*. “The visitor is someone who could come at any moment, without any horizon of expectation, who could like the Messiah come by surprise. Anyone could come at any moment” (Derrida [2000], p.17, n. 17). Hospitality is the unconditional welcoming of the *arrivant*. “The absolute guest [*hôte*] is this *arrivant* for whom there is not even a horizon of expectation, who bursts onto my horizon of expectations when I am not even prepared to receive the one who I’ll be receiving. That’s hospitality” (Derrida [2007], p. 451). The arrival of the *arrivant* will constitute an event, says Derrida (2007), “only if I’m not capable of receiving him or her” (p. 451). Unconditional hospitality is the welcoming of such event.

Throughout this work, it has been an issue of freeing, as Derrida (2007) puts it, the “pure eventfulness of the event” (p. 134) from the traditional attempts to neutralize it, whether through the demands of a principle of reason or through the position of a willful ego.¹ As we also stressed, the event is an absolute *arrivance* (“what is true for the *arrivant* is equally true for the event” [Derrida (2007), p. 453]), which as such mobilizes a welcoming gesture. We noted the coming to the fore of the motif of “letting” in the happening of the event. This letting also affects the welcome of the event. To the letting of being (subjective genitive) corresponds the fundamental disposition of thinking as *Gelassenheit*, as letting-be. Ethics here designates such letting, a genuine *Gelassenheit* with respect to the event. This arrival is welcomed in an original hospitality, a welcome of the other in the subjective genitive. We noted throughout this work how the event happens outside knowledge, in excess of knowledge, thereby making room for another type of engagement with the event, i.e., an ethical engagement. Whereas knowledge, as Levinas claims, is a violence, ethics understood as unconditional hospitality lets the event be. Thinking the event thus leads us to an ethical engagement with its unpredictable arrival.

¹ Although, as Derrida (2007) notes, there is always an aporetic element to this question, as the event becomes each time neutralized by its reception. If on the one hand, the saying of the event “remains or should remain disarmed, utterly disarmed by ... the always unique, exceptional, and unpredictable arrival of the other, of the event as other,” yet “this disarmament, this vulnerability, and this exposure are never pure or absolute. I was saying before that the saying of the event presupposed some sort of inevitable neutralization of the event by its iterability, that saying always harbors the possibility of resaying” (p. 452).

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The Enigmatic Figure of Socrates in Heidegger: A Pure Vision of Education as Attuned Event of Learning¹

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Introduction

This essay elucidates a view of “Heidegger’s Socrates” with the understanding that Socrates, unlike Plato, is a highly enigmatic figure in the Heideggerian corpus. In what follows, I attempt to sketch a portrait of Socrates—as a decidedly “non-doctrinal” philosopher or thinker—from an understanding of Heidegger’s philosophy in a way that might be related to a unique vision of education (*paideia*) as a philosophical *way-of-Being*, or perhaps, and more appropriately, given Heidegger’s explicit and unwavering task during the “Turn,” a mode of “pure thinking” unfolding in the relationship with the *truth-of-Being*, which is at once an *originary* educative event. Ultimately, turning to a view of Heidegger’s Socrates, I offer a counter view to such common educational issues as the employment of *methods*, the means of *knowledge acquisition*, and the understanding of the *learning process* as they comprise the educational experience in the age of standardization and the rise and dominance of STEM curricula. The essay unfolds in three sections: (1) I explore Heidegger’s analysis of Plato and discuss how the metaphysics that can be drawn from Plato’s philosophy influences our conception and practice of education; (2) I offer a detailed analysis of *pure thinking*, *truth*, and *dialectic method* in relation to “Heidegger’s Socrates,” which includes insights on how this view might be clarified and enhanced by turning to a non-doctrinal interpretation of Plato’s Socrates emerging from recent scholarship focused on re-readings of the Platonic corpus; and (3) I synthesize the foregoing analyses with a view of education (*paideia*), attempting to elucidate a unique vision of a *Socratic education* in the spirit of Heidegger’s reading, which lives beyond the understanding of philosophy akin to a science and education understood as a standardized, controllable, and predictable technological achievement. In relation to (2), a unique approach is adopted, which includes, because of the lack of detailed material written by Heidegger about Socrates, consulting works that are not explicitly Heideggerian in theme or content, e.g., turning to Continental Platonic scholarship which will assist in showing *how* key ideas emerging from Heidegger’s reading of Socrates *might* be understood when further illuminated by similar writings embracing Socrates, as does Heidegger, as a radically “non-doctrinal” and “non-systematic” thinker.

The Question of Heidegger’s Plato: Truth as Correctness in Relation to Education

Heidegger is often criticized in Platonic circles (Gonzalez 2009; Zuckert 1999), and by Continental “phenomenological” Platonic interpretation (Hyland 1995) and Heideggerian scholarship (Poggler 1987), for developing and espousing a “doctrinal” view of Plato’s philosophy. For example,

¹ It is with much appreciation that I thank the editor of this symposium, Elias Schwieler, for suggesting that I contribute this paper. I am also grateful to Richard Capobianco for offering helpful commentary on several sections of the paper, which contributed greatly to its overall improvement. Lastly, I thank the *JPSE* reviewers for their suggestions, specifically regarding the inclusion of a short discussion of *Gelassenheit*.

Gonzalez states emphatically that the “figure who normally bears the name ‘Plato’ in Heidegger’s text is a *dogmatic metaphysician*,” and we add, the first systematic metaphysician and, as is related directly to our concern, “the complete antithesis to the figure Heidegger himself names ‘Socrates’” (p. 431, emphasis added). Against Heidegger, Hyland offers a decidedly “non-doctrinal” reading of Plato, stating that Heidegger’s “reading ... of the cave analogy in *Plato’s Doctrine of Truth* is cursory and orthodox [doctrinal] to the point of tediousness” (p. 140). As stated, to embrace Heidegger’s reading of Plato’s philosophy (i.e., metaphysics) as doctrinal in nature is not limited to Platonic scholars, for Poggler (1987), commenting on Heidegger’s *path of thinking*, also claims that Heidegger presents Plato as a doctrinal metaphysician, whose philosophy is grounded in a systematic view of both metaphysics and education—a philosophy that contributes to facilitating the birth and flourishing of the historical movement of secular humanism.¹ Prior to attempting to understand Heidegger’s Socrates, it is crucial to address the question of Heidegger’s “doctrinal” Plato, because it is possible to encounter a different Plato that escapes the rigid classification as a doctrinal philosopher, i.e., in terms of a systematic metaphysician, present to Heidegger’s readings found in at least three texts other than the well-known essay we later examine, “Plato’s Doctrine of Truth,” and those sources are *The Basic Problems of Phenomenology*, *On the Essence of Truth*, and “Will to Power as Art.” As Fried (2006) observes, although in Plato there undoubtedly occurs “the transition of truth as *aletheia* from unconcealment (*Unverborgenheit*) to the correctness of representation,” this “error” is irreducible to the expression of a tenet or principle within an explicit philosophical doctrine, for we must be clear that when Heidegger employs the term “doctrine” (*Lehre*), he refers to “‘that which, within what is said, remains unsaid,’ rather than a self-conscious teaching of the thinker” (p. 157). Although space does not allow for an overly detailed exploration of this issue, I examine, in connection to Heidegger’s writings, the scholarship of both Fried and Capobianco (2010) in the effort to arrive at a deeper and re-conceived understanding of Heidegger’s interpretation of Plato.

Fried (2006), in his reading of Plato as a non-doctrinal thinker, points out that many times Heidegger “insists even in specific readings of Plato’s texts, that he is confronting not Plato but Platonism” (p. 157). This issue becomes explicit when examining Heidegger’s reading of Nietzsche as the *last metaphysician* in the “Will to Power as Art,” where it is clear that in reading Nietzsche, Heidegger (1979) is dealing with “Platonism” and not Plato as he might be understood when traced back to his original dialogues. There is a gaping historical chasm between Plato the philosopher and Plato the systematic, doctrinal metaphysician, i.e., between Plato and *Platonism*. It is Nietzsche, when presenting in *Twilight of the Idols* (“How the ‘True World’ Finally Became Fable”) the “portrayal of the history of Platonism and its overcoming” (p. 203) who, according to

¹ It is crucial to examine the term doctrinal or idealist in relation to Platonic scholarship in order to highlight characteristics consistent with systematic readings, as we have pointed out, that are relatable in some degree to Heideggerian interpretations of Plato. These characteristics of “doctrinal” or “idealist” readings are also linked to the analytic tradition, e.g., Sahakian and Sahakian (1976) read Plato as a systematic metaphysical *idealist* and embrace the notions that (1) Knowledge “produced” by the dialectic is propositional in nature; (2) The dialectic, as method *sine qua non* of the Philosopher-Rulers, culminates in *noesis* by transcending the *hypothetical method* in the production of certain truth; (3) Knowledge accruing via the dialectic is of the essential “Forms” and ultimately the “Idea” of the Good; and (4) The “positive” experience of the dialectic, which is equated with “Socratic” education, is substantive, definitive, and reproducible.

Heidegger, “establishes” and attaches a doctrinal, two-tiered metaphysics to Plato, as famously represented by the irreconcilable division between the sensuous realm of terrestrial dwelling and the supersensuous, eternal realm of the transcendental Forms (p. 202). Thus, Heidegger claims that Nietzsche’s understanding emerges through *creative interpretation*, for Plato’s original work “is not yet Platonism,” and further, the “‘true world’ is not yet the object of a doctrine, [rather] it is what lights up in becoming present; it is pure radiance without cover” (p. 204). Fried (2006) argues that Plato moves away from “the conflictual heart of truth as unconcealment” in favor of the movement toward truth as “genuine transcendence,” and in doing so, Plato misses, or better, fails to formalize what remains “unsaid” and only intimated in his philosophy, namely, that we “cannot possess [truth as *aletheia*] because we do not own or master history or fate” (p. 170). Moving forward, I show that Heidegger’s philosophy is more akin to Plato’s original thought, or view of philosophy, in more ways than many commentators might care to admit.¹

Recall the meaning of *Lehre* in Heidegger from the discussion above, and relate this understanding to Capobianco’s (2010) illuminating analysis of “light” and “lighting” in Heidegger’s reading of Plato, which reveals that in Heidegger’s reading, what is and remains “unsaid,” that which resides beneath the surface of what Plato “said,” admittedly, through representational imagery—and not the *logos* proper—is that the Idea of the “Good,” which is beyond the Forms, is also beyond, and so more primordial than, either beings or Being(ness). This indicates that Plato’s thought is occurring in the midst of, but is unable to explicitly formalize, the lighting and enabling power (*dem ursprünglichen Licht*) of Being itself. As Capobianco contends, “Plato’s Idea of the Good is no ‘it’ at all,” in terms of an immutable, eternal *essence*, nor is it a *normative* ideal toward which to strive; rather, it is “to be understood as the (temporal) ‘enabling’ (*ermöglichend*) of all beings in their beingness” (p. 105), as the “condition of the possibility” for all knowledge and truth about beings in their beingness (p. 106). Following Heidegger, Capobianco brings attention to, in relation to the *cave allegory*, the sun (*ἡλιος*) as the primordial light (*φως*), as the enabling power (*δυναμις*) that makes possible and links together (*ζυγον*), i.e., the ontological relationship between, what is seen in its presencing (*‘ορομενα*) and the “seeing” relating to the original experience or event of presencing (*‘οραν*) as a phenomenon in terms of *aletheia*. Plato did relate the Forms to light and lighting, as a “kind of letting-through—namely, a letting something be known as what it is in its full look (*eidos*), presence, whatness, beingness,” and although this “aspect of Plato’s thinking ultimately served as the foundation for the Western onto-theological tradition with its focus on timeless and immutable ‘essences’ of particular things,” as Capobianco importantly points out, “the allegory reveals to us that Plato’s thinking did not come to rest at this point” (p. 106), and with the Idea of the Good (as the lighting of Being itself), he appears to be thinking beyond the Forms and did not, as Aristotle claims, organize such thinking into a coherent and systematic account of metaphysical essences, paradigms, or concrete universals. Drawing a crucial connection between Heidegger’s Plato and Heidegger’s philosophy, Capobianco

¹ Although there is an ongoing scholarly debate about the doctrinal nature of Heidegger’s Plato, it is certainly the case that in the tradition of *Platonism*, Plato is read as either having a complete system expressed in an esoteric manner to initiates or a developing system evolving across Plato’s “early,” “middle,” and “late” periods of his life and philosophy, and indeed, as related to our themes, such interpretations of Plato as a systematic metaphysician are still taught in universities to philosophy students.

demonstrates that the notion of *die Lichtung* in *Being and Time* is traceable to Heidegger's early readings of Plato and develops in Heidegger's later thought. The lighting and enabling power of Being that Plato intimates in the *allegory* is the event and occurrence of "lighting" within which Dasein participates when revealing and founding and grounding a world and appropriating a historical destiny.¹ Ontologically, Dasein is set within "the light that is the source of all that is seen in the light," and not "in the first place, an ontic entity that possesses the 'natural light' of reason" (p. 106), and though Heidegger does not weave the interpretation of the *allegory* into *Being and Time*, it is, as Capobianco argues, "clearly in the background of his thinking," for Heidegger appropriates "Plato's metaphor of light in order to articulate his primary concern with that which *enables* the truth of all beings in their beingness" (p. 107).

To return to the understanding of *Lehre* in Heidegger, based on the forgoing analysis, I am not reading Plato as a thinker consciously aware of establishing or developing a system or doctrine of thought in the modern sense of the term. What is instead suggested is that due to Plato's inability to properly formalize or "say" what was always already present to his philosophical experience—that which ultimately remained "unsaid"—the essence of truth as *aletheia* as primordial concealment and the concern for Being as such were issues subsequently covered over and obscured. In direct and succinct terms: since the enabling power of Being, which is rooted in its recession and move into finitude, was overlooked by Plato, so too was the essence of truth as *aletheia* as primordial unconcealment, which is linked ineluctably and intimately to the phenomenon of Being's unfolding. As related directly to my concerns, Heidegger (1997) observes that Plato's *allegory* is an experience of *aletheia*, but in Plato's philosophy, "the fundamental experience from which that word $\alpha\text{-}\lambda\eta\theta\epsilon\iota\alpha$ arose is already disappearing"—i.e., the *originary* pre-Socratic experience of truth—and thus it does not come to "light in its primordially or essence" because Plato is unable, or falls into error due to a "failure" (*Verfehlung*) or "mistake" (*Versehen*), to formalize truth in its essence, in the *antagonistic* "characteristic of $\phi\upsilon\sigma\iota\varsigma$ (being), to the $\kappa\rho\upsilon\pi\tau\epsilon\sigma\theta\alpha\iota\ \phi\iota\lambda\epsilon\iota$ ("nature's affinity for remaining hidden"), thus to hiddenness as such and not just to the false, not just to illusion" (p. 68). This error, through which *aletheia* is neither *clarified* nor *grasped*, spawns Western metaphysics, for in Plato the "word [*aletheia*] and its semantic power is already on the road to impoverishment and trivialization" (68). Thus, although Plato's philosophy marks for Heidegger (1998) the beginning of Western onto-theological metaphysics, it is possible to interpret this "beginning" in terms that are other than Plato's formulation and foundation of anything resembling a doctrinal metaphysics; this, it is possible to state, was left to Plato's predecessors. Despite this insight, which should inspire rethinking Plato as a doctrinal thinker,² I move to examine several topics that are unambiguous in Heidegger's (1997) reading of Plato, namely, the influence of Platonic metaphysics—or *Platonism*—on our

¹ Turning to Sheehan (2001), the "enabling power" of which I am speaking makes possible and so is "responsible for the *correlation* between an entity's givenness and the dative of that givenness" (p. 7). This enabling power is named by Heidegger as "*ein drittes*," and insofar as it "makes *Parousia* possible, this enabling power is *epekeina tes parousias*, 'beyond' beings-as-givenness, in a way that is analogous to what Plato called *to agathon* [the Good]" (p. 8). Sheehan's reading on this issue lines up, in many ways, with Capobianco's interpretation as presented above.

² See also: Minca, B. (2015). "Heidegger's Interpretation of the Platonic *Cave Allegory Theatetus* (1931/32) as Early Indication of *Kehre* and *Ereignis*," *Eudia*, Vol. 9 (9), 1-14.

conception of and experience of truth, and how this understanding shapes our practice and experience of education, and I approach these issues in terms of “a *questioning* which in a fundamental way changes Dasein, man, and the understanding of being” (p. 84).

“Plato’s Doctrine (*Lehre*) of Truth,” one of Heidegger’s (1998) most well-known readings of Plato’s Allegory of the Cave, elucidates a view of metaphysics that emerges from Plato’s philosophy of the essence of truth (*aletheia*) with the concomitant understanding of *how* the essence of truth ultimately determines an authentic view of education as *paideia*. Authentic education (*paideia*), for Heidegger, in his reading of Plato and the Allegory, is represented in a series of “movements” as the turning around (*periagoge*) of the entire soul back to itself enlightened, i.e., an authentic education “lays hold of the soul itself and transforms it in its entirety by first leading us to the place of essential Being accustoming us to it” (p. 165). This, however, is the precise form of *originary* education that a Platonic view of metaphysics, with its privileging of *presencing* over concealment and its focus on the Being of beings as opposed to Being *qua* Being, ultimately fails to realize. As immersed in the Platonic tradition, we experience the *essence* of truth in terms of an *epistemological* and not an *ontological* issue, for it is taken as the “agreement” or relation between idea and thing as expressed through a locution or proposition, where the *locus* of truth is encountered, e.g., as in the history of Western philosophy and the understanding of *adaequatio intellectus et rei* (“agreement between intellect (idea) and thing”), expressed through the *Correspondence Model of Truth*. According to Heidegger, due to this misinterpretation of *aletheia*, Plato’s vision of knowing and learning, or “education,” does not rise to the level of *paideia* and rather is represented by *gignoschein*, the process of “knowing by way of seeing,” and this is linked by Heidegger with the Greek *idein* in relation to *idea* in terms of *homoiosis*, as exclusively the overall “agreement of the act of knowing with the thing itself” as seen (p. 177).

Truth is inseparable from education, and following this line of thought, since the “first beginning” and Plato’s error education moves away from an original notion of *paideia* as it is instantiated within the soul’s relation to the truth of Being; *learning* is no longer an open questioning grounded in finitude, mystery, and primordial hiddenness, attuned in wonder or “astonishment” (*das Erstaunen*), and is instead systematically “harnessed in a relation to looking, apprehending, thinking, and asserting” (p. 182). This because, according to Heidegger (1997), education’s ontological origin in the experience of *aletheia* is occluded, and so we fail to realize the deeper truth that *aletheia* can never be arbitrarily possessed like propositional truths, “whose enjoyment we put aside at some point in order to instruct or lecture other people” (p. 66). This leads to a view of education that is directed toward the accumulation and possession of knowledge—established truths above falsehoods. Indeed, as Heidegger (1993) argues, if we were to receive a so-called “good education,” we would then “know everything possible to know in all realms of science, art, and the like,” and we would continue to “acquire each day what is newest and most valuable” (p. 258). This is a view of education, resulting from the fallout of *Platonism*, which can be equated with models of teaching-learning instantiated within contemporary education; it is a form of education that Scott (2001), in his reading of Plato’s Socrates’ non-doctrinal practice of education, claims is akin to an *additive model of education*, the very type of education—the filling up of empty vessels, the piling and building up of knowledge—that Plato’s Socrates continually decries

in the dialogues,¹ which stands radically opposed to an *integrative model of education*, which might be associated with an original form of *paideia*. In relation to these thoughts, Heidegger (1993) observes that when thinking in education is conceived as a “technique for explaining highest causes,” it comes to an “end by slipping out of its element,” and it then achieves its “validity as *techne*, as an instrument of education and therefore as a classroom matter,” in terms of what we understand as the *standardization* of education—and as Heidegger stresses, this presupposes it is already a “cultural concern” (p. 221). Drawing on Heidegger’s interpretation, I note that today in education we encounter a *technological-and-quantitative* view of the three educational issues this essay discusses: (1) *method* is understood as a top-down, transposable schema for “problem-solving” (scientific method) or “teaching”; (2) *truth* is conceived (and experienced) as the destination to which method inevitably leads, i.e., knowledge as something that is acquired, possessed, and validated by one or another epistemological model (e.g., Correspondence Model of Truth); and (3) *learning* is a controllable, predictable, and terminal activity that occurs through the successful application of a given method, indicating that truth has been procured, which is then assessed to indicate the student’s or learner’s educational achievement.²

¹ For example, in the *Symposium*, Socrates assures Agathon that authentic education can neither be pursued nor carried out as a process through which those who have little in the way of knowledge are made more knowledgeable by those possessing greater knowledge, as “if ideas were the kind of things which could be imparted simply by contact, and those of us who had few could absorb them from those who have a lot,” much like the “way that liquid can flow from a full container to an empty one if you put a piece of string between them” (175d).

² Overlooking the plausible conclusion offered by many Platonic scholars regarding the lack of a codified method in Plato’s Socrates, Socratic Circles, Socratic Method, and Socratic Seminar (Wilberding 2014; Strong 1997) are all formalized Socratic Methods for application in the classroom. Educators implementing Socratic Seminars argue that Socrates employs a *reproducible* systematic method that can be explicated, packaged, marketed, taught, and applied in the classroom to produce definitive “academic” results that meet the criteria for the objectives in Common Core State Standards Curriculum and the concomitant high-stakes testing consistent with the contemporary standardized view of education. These educators claim that Socrates’ way of practicing his dialectic examination can be systematized and *imitated*. In relation to this claim, we bring the reader’s attention to a crucial issue that Plato highlights in the *Apology*, to which practitioners of the Socratic method in education have apparently paid no heed or have summarily dismissed, namely, the utterly and unmistakably disastrous results that ensued when the youths of Athens attempted to “imitate” the enigmatic and inimitable Socrates. Those who *imitated* Socrates contributed to the formulation of the charges against him, as they systematized, copied, and employed his supposed “method,” performing *elenchus* refutations of prominent Athenian citizens. Let us listen to Socrates, who proclaims, “The sons of the richest men accompany of their own accord, find pleasure in *hearing people being examined*, and often imitate me themselves, and then they undertake to examine others; and then, I fancy, they find a great plenty of people who think they know something, but know little or nothing. As a result, therefore, those who are examined by them are angry with me” (Plato 1997, *Apol.* 23c-e). It is interesting to note, in relation to “Socratic teaching,” that as opposed to training or teaching (*didasko*) these youths to be upstart “gadflies,” it is by chance (*tuche*), and neither by Socratic design nor the implementation of any

Heidegger's Socrates: Pure Thinking in the Sway of the Unfolding of Essential Truth

Heidegger (1968) labels Socrates the “purest thinker of the West” (p. 17), and it is this classification as a “pure thinker” that I am committed to unpacking as it relates to Socrates’ understanding and practice of dialectic, his view of “truth,” and his understanding of philosophy (or thinking) as a process of original learning (*paideia*). Heidegger observes that Socrates is courageously “drawn to what withdraws” in the process of enacting the authentic process of *thinking*, which draws him into “the enigmatic and therefore mutable nearness of its appeal,” despite being “far away from what withdraws,” and even though “the withdrawal may remain as veiled as ever” (p. 17). This instantiates for Heidegger the “living context” of thinking, a context facilitating the “draft” of the dynamic counter-striving of lighting and primordial concealing, and Socrates, according to Heidegger, did “nothing else than place himself into this draft, this current, and maintain himself in it,” and this is why, according to Heidegger he was the *purest thinker of the West* (p. 17).¹ To bring clarity to this notion of thinking in terms of an immersion in the “draft,” I turn to Heidegger’s (1999) interpretation of what he terms Da-sein’s *Being-historical thinking* (*inceptual/mindful thinking*), which is an original way of doing philosophy, or more correctly, *thinking*, “according to more *originary* basic stance,” within the context sheltering the unfolding of “the question of the truth of be-ing,” which is no longer a “thinking about something and representing something objective” (p. 3), but rather a *thinking of* matters in the *poietic* manner of *bringing forth* what is thought in its incompleteness while at once retaining and sheltering traces and intimations of its supreme and primordial power, which inspires the respect for the ineffability of that which is thought, for there is a refusal of “that-which-is-thought” to be brought to full disclosure or rendered wholly intelligible in language.

For Heidegger, it is Being *qua* Being or the essential truth of Being that is thought as the grounding ontological topic. With respect to Socrates, as is known from the dialogues (especially the “early” dialogues, which are *aporetic* in nature), what Heidegger speaks of might be related to the Being or ineffable and mysterious *essence* of the virtues, which Socrates continually and relentlessly questions within the context of his ever-renewed thought and examination. Heidegger (1999) claims that *inceptive-mindful thinking* is attuned in an original mode of questioning, which draws in and holds the thinker in the primordial “sway” of the relationship between thinking and the

formal or even informal “Socratic curriculum,” that these youths are drawn to Socrates, listen intently to him, and then take it upon themselves to *imitate* him (Magrini 2017; 2018).

¹ It is necessary to include, in this definition of “pure thinking” in relation to Socrates, another reason why Heidegger (1968) considers him a “pure thinker”: Socrates was unique in that he understood and embraced that what he philosophized and thought was ineffable in terms of written communication, and this of course extended for Heidegger beyond even the type of “allegory,” “metaphor,” and “mythology” Plato employed. “For anyone who begins to write out of thoughtfulness,” declares Heidegger, “must inevitably be like those people who run to seek refuge from any draft too strong for them,” for Socrates knew that when thinking, he was *pointing* “at something which has not, not yet, been transposed into the language of our speech” (pp. 17-18). The so-called elusive, hidden, and original “truths” which Socrates pursued could not be formulated linguistically, via the *logos*.

essential truth of Being. This type of thinking does not come to an end, for it is never a means to the end of truth that might terminate the thinking, and so is always actively *underway* as an ever-renewed *event* of thinking and questioning, or we might say, *learning*. It abides amid Being's essential unfolding, and as an experience of the *coming-to-be and passing-away of Being*, it breaks open and holds open what is most *question-worthy*. Heidegger claims that authentic thinkers are enraptured and attuned within the exigent and *distressing* need of "*holding [themselves] within the essential sway of truth*" (p. 258). This form of thinking shelters the *mystery*, or Being's recession into hiddenness (*Entrückung*) that initially facilitates unhiddenness (*Berückung*), illuminating beings in such a way that the event and truth of Being unfolds in its most primordial manner. This is one way to interpret Heidegger's comments regarding Socrates' *pure mode of thinking*, and in phenomenological non-doctrinal readings of Plato's Socrates, it is possible to understand the *questioning-context* of the dialectic as sheltering and instantiating the unfolding of Socrates' mode or practice of questioning, his mode of dialectic examination, which is directed toward the most *question-worthy* issues (e.g., Hyland 1995; Kirkland 2010).

Heidegger (1958) claims that Socrates thinks and hence is driven by a single thought, for he repeatedly thinks "on no other topic than what things are" and continues to say "the same thing about the same thing" (p. 74), and, as stated, this for Socrates is to attempt to wrest from concealment the *Being of the virtues*. He thinks the same thing because the matter demands an unwavering dedication to continually return to it, responding to its enigmatic withdrawal and appeal, because its very essence resists being exhausted by the questioning; it defies acquisition and possession, and this is because, as stated, what Socrates inquires into always remains essentially open-ended and hence *question-worthy*. To think such thoughts we must first, states Heidegger (1968), "incline toward what addresses itself to thought" or "that which of itself gives food for thought," and this he identifies as a *gift*, and the "gift of what must be properly be thought about, is what we call most thought-provoking" (p. 17)—i.e., that which is most *question-worthy*. This I relate directly to the "the question" Socrates asks, which finds its origin (*archē*) or beginning (*Ursprung*) in an attunement or *pathos* Heidegger calls "astonishment" (*das Erstaunen*) as related to "wonder" (*thauma*), and as Socrates explains in the *Theaetetus*, this attunement grounds philosophy.¹ When talking of the "beginning," Heidegger (1959) references *archē*, which "names that from which something proceeds"; however, that which emerges never truly leaves behind its origin or source, for the beginning is that which produces and also holds reigns over what is produced, for "the verb *achein* expresses, that which governs" (p. 81), i.e., *astonishment* and *wonder* give birth to and continue to nourish, invigorate, and direct Socrates' ever-renewed philosophical inquiry. In short, turning to Capobianco (2010), "*philosophia* begins—and ends—in 'astonishment'" (p. 83). In and through "wonder" we are set within a relationship to what is inquired into, and here recall my initial comments regarding Socrates and the "draft" of thinking, wherein that which is questioned, that which is essential, "retreats" from our advances, as we are held in a state of "wonder" or "astonishment" and simultaneously drawn into the inquiry and

¹ In relation to our treatment of the attunement of *originary* thinking, Capobianco (2010) reminds us that *pathos* is related to *paschein*, the suffering and enduring through a mood or mode of attunement, and the Greeks' and Heidegger's understanding of *pathos* "is far removed from the modern psychological understanding of inward subjective feelings and emotions"; rather, *pathos* is more "originally understood as the way in which the human being is 'attuned' and 'disposed' by Being" (p. 83).

secured there by that which recedes from or retreats from our grasp. Out of this phenomenon spring forth what Heidegger (2000) terms “original questions,” and these original questions never terminate in definitive answers; they can never be closed-off or solved in terms of problems, and the most original question for Socrates, as Heidegger informs us, is the “Greek *ti estin*,” or “What is the essence of *x*?” Since philosophy has as its beginning (*archē*) *Erstaunen*, original questions also have their origin in the *pathos* of astonishment, and this beginning, according to Heidegger, gives rise to a questioning that “pushes [Socrates] into the open,” and as an original questioning, it “transforms itself (as does every genuine questioning), and casts a new space over and through everything” (p. 32).

The type of truth consistent with doctrinal or idealist readings of Plato’s Socrates focuses on knowledge that can be grounded, as we saw in Heidegger’s reading of Plato, in “correctness,” but contrarily, Heidegger’s Socrates might be said, as Kirkland (2010) contends, to devote himself to the pursuit of “truth,” which presupposes an “attitude toward his subject matter in which he does not impose his will upon it,” because it can’t be a pure *object* of his thought; rather, he “aims to allow it to *come to light* in his discourse” (p. 51, my emphasis). This is strikingly similar to the manner in which Plato (1997) in *Letter Seven* describes *philosophical understanding* as an original occurrence of *aletheia*, which manifests in dialogue, but “cannot at all be expressed” or captured precisely “in words as other studies can, but instead, from living with the subject itself in frequent dialogue a light is [eventually] kindled and a *leaping flame* comes to [settle] in the soul where it presently nourishes itself” (341b-d, emphasis added). I want to explore this notion of Socratic truth as it might relate to Heidegger’s philosophy in a bit more detail by looking to the early Greek experience of *aletheia*, which is by now quite familiar to readers of Heidegger, as an encounter with unhiddenness (un-concealment) linked intimately with hiddenness (concealment) as the ground for its possibility, the possibility of entities *presencing* or showing up for our appropriation—in their *givenness*—in the first instance. As previously stated, Heidegger (2002) finds the original understanding of *aletheia* in Heraclitus’ Fragment 123: *φύσις ... κρυπτεσθία φιλει*, which might be translated in a straightforward manner as “Nature has an affinity for hiding or remaining hidden.” To relate this idea to the language of the “sway” within which Socrates *thinks*, it is within the midst of the sway that the Being of beings “loves to conceal itself” (p. 9). This Heideggerian understanding of *aletheia* is stressed in Kirkland’s (2010) non-idealist reading of Plato’s Socrates in pursuit of the *phenomenal Being* of the virtues. In the course of questioning and interrogating the initial appearance of the virtue present to the *doxai*, as opposed to definitions or ideas filling the content of consciousness, “what emerges into truth through the questioning of the *doxa* with Socrates is ‘what virtue *is*’” (p. 115), but this truth cannot be brought to stand in propositional language, and rather must remain in an incomplete form. Indeed, Socrates’ *living-with* the appearance and instantiation of this truth, which like a *flashing light* attunes, nourishes, and enlivens the soul, represents the true success or positive aspect of the dialectic, for “it marks the [ontological] limit of virtue’s appearing to us, disturbing our *doxai* and pointing thereby beyond them to what is present in *doxa* only in exceeding it” (p. 115).

In his analysis of the *pathein-of-truth* (“suffering under” truth), Kirkland argues that the experience of *aletheia* is not only “excessive” it can also be “dangerous” in the sense of opening us up to an encounter with *ta deinon*, or the *awe-inspiring* presence of truth, which “resists being delimited and made intelligible, not merely frustrating our specific expectations, but radically calling into question what we presumed to be the limits of ‘what is,’ even of the possible” (p. 49). Here, we

can understand Heidegger’s claim regarding Socrates as a “pure thinker” demonstrating the courage to hold himself in the dialectic’s unfolding and resisting the temptation to *flee-in-the-face* of truth, to which many interlocutors ultimately fall victim. *Aletheia*, as *philosophical understanding*, manifests as the *flashing flame* within a momentary revelation, as an *intimation of truth*, where there is the concomitant movement or recession of what disappears into mystery, and certain aspects of the virtue Socrates interrogates—including its very *essence*—remain concealed (Magrini 2017; 2018). Thus, as opposed to the type of propositional or axiomatic certainty that many analytic or Anglo interpreters of Plato link with the (potential) philosopher-rulers’ practice of the dialectic in the *Republic*, it is possible to grasp Socrates’ notion of *philosophical understanding*, as would be consistent with Heidegger’s portrayal of Socrates, as intimated and poetized by Heidegger, in the following manner, which I have formalized: (1) it is a form of *insight* that although emerging from an interactive and discursive process of dialogue, it itself non-discursive; (2) it is non-propositional, but it is irreducible to rote or basic “know-how,” this because it is both an *ontological* and “normative” form of *insight*; (3) it is manifest and *comes-to-presence* only in the midst of dialogue or the practice of the philosophical method; (4) it is neither wholly subjective nor objective and rather *mediates* both realms; it is also reflexive in nature as a potential form of “self-knowledge” (Gonzalez 1998; Kirkland 2010; Hyland 1995). It is now to the issue of the practice of dialectic in Heidegger’s Socrates that I turn.

When separating the sophist off from Socrates—or Socratic philosophy—the real philosopher, the *ontos philosophos*, Heidegger (1997a) describes Socrates as embodying the vocation, task, or occupation that looks upon the *bios*, as this term and concept is set off from *zōē*. This indicates for Heidegger that the philosopher is not concerned with the life of things and entities set within the “nexus of animals and plants, of everything that crawls and flies,” but rather directed toward the “sense of existence, the leading of a life, which is characterized by a determinate *telos*, a *telos* functioning for the *bios*, itself as an object of *praxis*” (p. 168), and for this reason, philosophy is a *way-of-Being* in the world. The philosopher is concerned with living out various kinds of life, and most importantly, makes a determination regarding the best type of life to live. For Socrates, as already stated, this is a life in pursuit of virtue, excellence, and the “good”; it is a life that is inseparable from the practice of the dialectic or *dialektikē*—the practice and *way-of-Being* that is at once a living with the *logoi*. Unlike typical doctrinal or idealist readings of Plato that view the dialectic as a tool or trusted method for arriving at certain truth, truth grasped in and through *noein*—beyond *dianoia* where the *hypothetical method* is jettisoned, as described in the *Republic*—Heidegger focuses on the dialectic’s flaws, revealing problems that Plato does not overcome. Gonzalez (1997), in his reading of the *Sophist*, informs us that according to Heidegger, the “*logos* pervading all forms of disclosing ... has a tendency to conceal”; as such, what the dialectic aims at is what amounts to the transcendence of language or the *logos* by way of “proceeding *through* (dia) *logos*,” and “its ultimate aim, that towards which it is inherently directed, must be a pure seeing or *noein* beyond *logos*” (p. 18). However, the dialectic can never accomplish this end and so has an “inherent tendency toward a ‘pure seeing’ that it can never attain” (p. 19). At first blush, this appears to render the dialectic a failed project; however, this does not sound the death-knell for the dialectic in Socratic philosophy, for there are positive elements associated with the dialectic as practiced by Socrates, despite its failing to rise to the level of epistemological trustworthiness granted in doctrinal or idealist readings of Plato. It is successful within limits, and there are positive aspects of the Socratic dialectic that relate to truth, education, and the potential development of our character and disposition (*hexis*).

If, as Heidegger argues, the dialectic is limited, what then can it accomplish as related directly to a “Socratic” philosophy? In a response requiring some explanation, I show that the dialectic is both essential and beneficial to a philosophical life, as described above, in that it instantiates a living-practice and way-of-Being that is educational or *heuristically educative* in its essence, in terms of Heidegger’s understanding of *paideia* as initially described. The dialectic is a process that is *disclosive*; however, according to Gonzalez (1997), what it discloses it does so “indirectly, negatively, and ‘reflexively’ (i.e., through the process of philosophy itself)” (p. 38). When speaking of disclosing things “negatively,” this for Heidegger (1997) means a “denial by way of *legein*,” which indicates that “saying ‘no,’ is a letting be seen,” but always in a limited and incomplete manner. Negation in the dialectic for Heidegger, and here I include Socrates, possesses a “disclosive character,” in that within the denial of a line of argumentation or position, an encounter with the *aporetic breakdown* of examination, “within the concrete [but limited] uncovering of beings,” denial serves a “purifying [cathartic] function, so that negation itself acquires a productive character” (p. 388). Negation is understood by Heidegger as an integral component of the Socratic dialectic, which is thought of as a process of “*καθαρσις* of the *αγοια* by *ελεγχος*,” which works by “setting the *δοχαι* against each other through the *συναγειν εις ‘εν*” (p. 260)—i.e., the *purification* of ignorance through the questioning and *synthesizing* through the *gathering* of beliefs and opinions held by those who are engaged in the dialogue, which importantly includes the process of winnowing out those beliefs and opinions determined untenable. In this process, what is positive for Socrates is the partial and limited revelation of the matter under discussion, i.e., the partial appearance of and glimpse into elusive *phenomenal Being* of the virtues. Here recall Plato’s claim in *Letter Seven* regarding the *leaping flame* of truth that settles in the soul, which transforms it through *periagoge*, or the soul’s *turning back* or *around* to itself enlightened, which is an “educative” (*paideutic*) occurrence or *event*. What Heidegger indicates about what is positive in the dialectic is linked intimately with a “Socratic attitude,” which achieves the “positive only in actually carrying it out,” by living within the *draft* and *sway* of the *inquiry* and *not* in terms of the dialectic producing positive results in terms of truth that somehow stands at the end, and hence beyond, the inquiry itself (p. 368), i.e., we are transformed only within the dialectic, only within the process itself, and not by some result it might produce.¹ How this enlightenment occurs, however, is not clearly explicated by Heidegger; however, in relation to his reading, I explore this issue by turning to non-doctrinal readings of Plato’s Socrates’s practice of dialectic in the attempt to show that although never culminating in *noetic insight* of the so-called “truth” of the *essence* of virtue, the *logoi*, in rigorous, well-meaning discourse, does

¹ Heidegger (1988) defines phenomenology in precisely the same manner, as a “method” within which truth manifests that cannot be jettisoned once we have arrived at it, e.g., when talking of interpreting *facticity*, Heidegger is clear that this interpretation can be nothing other than “living” it, for only in interpretive activity is Dasein’s possibility for “becoming and being for itself” made known and pursued; *ερμηνευειν* (the interpreting of facticity), is a *method* for living and acquiring “an *understanding* of itself” (p. 11). This observation is made by Gonzalez (2009) when stating in his reading of Socrates, “the truth of philosophy is its method,” for “Socrates himself, at least as depicted in Plato, places much more emphasis on method than on results, not only because his discussions are often aporetic, but also, and more importantly, because he appears to value more the process of dialectic and dialogue than any outcome of this process” (p. 427).

demonstrate a revelatory capacity in the process of questioning, refuting (negating), and winnowing out opinions and beliefs that are shown to be problematic and questionable.

Heidegger describes the practice of the dialectic as a vigorous questioning (*διερωταν*) with the purpose of shaking one out of familiar and complacent modes of knowing whereby many *doxai* are brought together and set in tension in relation to that which is questioned. Within the unfolding interrogation, the *doxai* “slap each other in the face” (p. 261), and there occurs the “casting out [*απαλλαγη*] of ungentle *δοξαι*,” and a “clearing away,” or a “removal of what stands in the way of the *μαθηματα*, the proper positive learning” (p. 262), which demonstrates the function of “*εκβαλλειν*” (p. 258), the act of *casting out* ignorance and *transcending αμαθια* in a way that “clarifies” or “purifies” (*καθαρισις*) the soul. Indeed, when Heidegger describes the context of the Socratic dialectic, and here recall Heidegger’s description of the philosopher’s life as introduced above, it should not be conceived as “a dwelling with the material content of knowledge,” i.e., not a process privileging *content-over-method*, or propositional knowledge over a more vague and limited form of understanding; rather, it is a matter of “the Being of Dasein itself: to what extent does it dwell in *αληθευειν* [understanding/truth of the virtues and the “good” life] or in *αγνοι* [ignorance of the virtues and the “good” life]” (pp. 262). But how, returning to Heidegger’s critique of the dialectic, as a practice driven by and given structure within language, a process that cannot transcend language in the pursuit to arrive at a pure form of seeing (*noesis*) that is beyond the *logos*, is it possible to imagine truth emerging from a practice driven by and at once limited by language? Gonzalez (1997) observes that what philosophy requires is a form of speech, or manner of approaching discourse, that “*breaks through* speech in a process of ‘speaking for and against,’” in a way that might direct our “attention beyond what is said, thereby leading us more and more to the matter under discussion and letting it be seen” (p. 18). If we take into consideration what Heidegger has said regarding the Being of Dasein as representing the true philosopher’s concern in relation to what he claims about dialogue, perhaps it is possible to suggest a response to this query and concern related to Socratic dialectic. Heidegger (1968) informs us that if dialogue focuses exclusively on “what is directly said” and what might be directly known through this *saying*, dialogue “becomes halting and fruitless” (p. 178). However, if inquirers in the dialogue “involve each other in *that* realm and abode about which they are speaking,” i.e., situate themselves in close proximity to the Being of that which is interrogated; and for Heidegger, as we have discussed, this is the realm of original questioning that gives rise to speaking in and from out of the “site of thought in its relation to the essential truth of Being,” and so opens the potential of dwelling “in the “soul of the dialogue” where the speakers are “led into the unspoken,” i.e., in this case, what emerges from the *logos* is irreducible to it (p. 178).

To approach an understanding of how this movement into the unspoken through the *logos* might occur in the unfolding of the Socratic dialectic, we consider Gonzalez’s (1998) and Gadamer’s (1988) insightful analyses of Plato’s *Letter Seven*, focusing on the manner in which the *four ways* of knowing contend in order to open a space for the *presencing* of the “fifth way,” or brief insight into a truth *barely seen* in the midst of the dialectic. I now consider how this phenomenon might occur through the winnowing process of *clearing away* the *negative* and making space for the *positive* in dialectic as Heidegger describes above. In *Letter Seven*, Plato (1997) discusses four ways of knowing: (1) names/words, (2) images/figures, (3) propositions, and (4) resulting insight (knowing). Plato also discusses a “fifth way” that occurs from these, a form of philosophical insight (*philosophical understanding*) that he stresses is ineffable; it cannot be spoken of like other

things philosophers discuss, and I note that it certainly does not possess the degree of certainty required to ground any systematic doctrine of philosophy (*EP VII 341c*). Whereas Heidegger elicits the imagery of the *doxai* “slapping against each other” within dialogic exchange, in both Gonzalez (1998) and Gadamer (1988), we encounter a similar metaphor, namely, that of the dialectic unfolding as process wherein the *doxai* or the “ways of knowing” are *rubbed* against each other, and this relates to the notion of language’s potential *transparency* in relation to the Greek term that Plato employs, *tribein*, “to rub down.”¹ Ideally, in the dialectic, we might imagine words fading into the background so that partial meaning shines forth. However, as Gadamer (1988) contends, in the “rubbing” together of the four ways in dialectic, language fails to achieve the level of full *transparency* required to let the “thing itself” (the Being of virtue) move to the fore unimpeded so as to be seen in the fullness of its self-showing (p. 105). Now, consider what Gonzalez (1998) contends about the Greek term *tribein*, as a “process of a *vigorous* rubbing that wears things down” (p. 265), or wears them away, and it is possible to understand the process of truth-happening in Plato’s *Letter Seven*, as this relates to the “negation” stressed in Heidegger’s reading of the dialectic: As we move through the four ways, rubbing each against the other, there occurs a “wearing down” of the language, so to speak. The more intensely we seek to clarify the names, images, and propositions we employ to ground our knowledge, the more the words/images begin to wear down and away; they recede, as it were, and a partial and momentary *transparency of language* occurs, and the fleeting light of truth shines forth, like a *leaping flame*. In more direct terms, according to Gonzalez (1998), through the “process of question and answer in which we *expose* the weakness of the words, propositions, and images we use”—through “negation”—we are afforded a momentary and partial vista onto truth, and “just barely glimpse through the cracks [opened in the process] the true being which they all attempt but fail to express” (p. 268). It is possible to link the “fifth way” of “barely” knowing the “thing itself” with the moment when language reaches its limited, but *disclosive* and “positive” potential as a *transparent medium* for *aletheia*.

This is not, however, to indicate that this form of insight transcends language usage entirely, or that it is a moment when truth is fully disclosed with no dissembling, because this moment of truth-happening occurs only in and through the vigorous use of language, which is always grounded in human limitation and radical finitude. As Gonzalez stresses, in a way related to this reading of Heidegger’s Socrates, this unique, fleeing, and fragile instance of *philosophical insight* as described is not and can never be “the kind of knowledge that will put an end to all inquiry or that can be ‘grasped’ once and for all” (p. 267), for it requires ever-renewed attempts to bring it to light, which requires the participants in the dialectic, as Heidegger has stressed in relation to Socrates, to strive to situate and hold themselves in the *draft* of the inquiry, for as Plato (1997) teaches,

¹ Original passages from Plato’s (1997) *Letter Seven* will assist the reader in understanding the analysis we have provided: “Only when all of these things—names, definitions, and visual and other perceptions—have been rubbed against one another and tested, pupil and teacher asking, and answering questions in good will and without enmity—only then, when reason and knowledge are at the very extremity of human effort, can they illuminate the nature of any object (344b) ... [but] this knowledge is not something that can be [put] into words like other sciences; but only after long-continued discourse between teacher and pupil, in joint pursuit of the subject, suddenly, like a light flashing forth when a fire is kindled, it is born of the soul and straightaway nourishes itself” (341c).

whatever “we learn” must be “learned together” [*synerchomai*], through long and earnest labor” (*EP VII 344b*). To further contribute to this line of thought as related to a theme already discussed, Kirkland (2010) stresses that the process of “truth-happening” highlights the *ontological distance* that the human being is situated from full disclosure of truth, which is always given in an obscure, oblique, and partially veiled manner. However, the dedicated participants in the pursuit of truth agree to inhabit the space, the “site of *distance* from but nonetheless *toward* the being of virtue” (xxii), and this indicates that we “abide with *doxa* while pointing beyond it and to its limits” (p. 114). In relation to what Kirkland identifies as the *deinos* associated with philosophical insight, what has been described is a *distressing distance* from Being, but one that is, in a sense and in an important way, wondrous and alluring—evoking the mood of “astonishment”—which establishes our relationship to issues that remain “as concealed, hidden, and thus questionworthy” (p. 55). We are drawn, as Heidegger indicates about Socrates, to the pursuit of that which withdraws from our grasp, and in its withdrawal it beckons us to continue our pursuit, because it is truly worthy of our continued questioning and represents the very *essence* of an education directed toward those things that are most beneficial for the development of the soul. The site of the dialectic, the ever-developing, ever-expanding context of *originary* learning, which is the locus of “*distance and the excess of truth*, belongs essentially to the site opened by *melete*,” which is related directly to Plato’s Socrates’ avowed practice of philosophy as *care for the soul* (as a *paideutic* practice), “by our being originally *concerned* with the being of virtue, compelled to be toward it in its withdrawal” (p. 114). We have more to say regarding this phenomenon, occurrence, or *event* in the concluding section below.

***Paideia* as Philosophical Task and Way-of-Being: A Socratic Notion of Truth-and-Method in Learning**

What I have described in these foregoing sections might be said to represent an *originary* understanding of *method* and *truth* in Socratic philosophy, as a practical way-of-Being or living out of one’s existence attuned to the understanding that this also instantiates a *life-of-learning*. In terms of what Heidegger describes, in relation to the undeniable Socratic influence on Plato’s thought, philosophy is a way of life, a *way-of-Being*, that is “on the way” (*unterwegs*) toward *learning*, which can never be equated with, to return to my earlier description of contemporary standardized education, the application of methods in the pursuit of acquiring sure and certain knowledge in education. Learning in a manner associated with Heidegger’s Socrates is never reducible to the rote accumulation of the day’s lessons, to be rehearsed on exams that calculate and assess the proficiency level of the student in memorizing and regurgitating the lesson; this is not Socratic learning, which I argue can never be authentically reproduced in the classroom, e.g., as is claimed by many embracing the so-called *Socratic Seminar*. Heidegger (1999) assures us of this when observing that *παιδεία* is not education in terms of transmission and accumulation of facts, linked with the *additive model* of learning; rather, it is “*πραγματεία*, a task, and hence not a self-evident possession,” and further, it is not merely a “task any person can take up according to whim but is one which precisely encounters in each person its own proper resistances” (p. 258). Heidegger (1968) recognizes that learning, just as is the case with *thinking*, is something we must first begin to “learn,” for learning in an essential way “means to make everything we do answer to whatever essentials address themselves to us at a given time” (p. 14). Education calls for, as opposed to the speaking of monologues or the delivering of lectures, an attuned mode of “listening” in advance for the call of education itself, and here I return to the *archē* of authentic philosophy—

from out of which we are attuned and continually guided and directed by the original issues we pursue and questions we ask—and the “unspoken” essence in dialogue, which reveals “truth” that partially and momentarily nourishes the soul, does so in such a way that we are at once challenged by it and attuned to continue on in the pursuit to better understand it, to bring to light further aspects of it that continue to recede from full disclosure.

Education, or authentic learning, as understood and practiced by Heidegger’s Socrates, is an ongoing and ever-renewed “task”—recall Heidegger’s understanding of education as “*πραγματεια*,” as exercise or labor—that is instantiated within the educational practice of dialectic, which according to Heidegger (1999), “provides the positive only in actually carrying it out and not by making it the direct theme of reflection” (p. 368), and then *producing* objective instances of knowledge that terminate the method or process.¹ Based on this speculative reading of Heidegger’s Socrates, what we term the *originary context of education*, which shelters the *draft of authentic thinking and learning*, unfolds in the following manner, grounded in the understanding that in learning there occurs a two-fold movement, captured by Heidegger’s use of the Greek term “*απαλλαγη*”: (1) our soul *moves away* from ignorance or *amathia*, and (2) because of the excessive and elusive nature of that which we seek to reveal, its essence *moves away* from us, living at an ontological remove from the scope and parameters of our inquires, and we are set at a distance from the full disclosure of the essence of what we are inquiring into.² Admittedly, if this two-fold movement fully captured the process we identify as *paidiea*, the situation of learning would indeed appear frustratingly pessimistic in the extreme. However, there is a third component that is inseparable from the movement that Heidegger importantly stresses, namely, that as we are attuned within this process, we are at once transformed; we are drawn toward and to the very thing that withdraws from our inquiry. In relation to this concern, I argue that authentic learning occurs within the dynamic “draft” created by the counter-striving movement between thought and *what is thought* set within the ontological context that instantiates our relationship to the essential truth

¹ In his reading of Socratic philosophy and the dialectic, Gonzalez (2004) stresses that philosophy is an endeavor where truth and method are inseparable, and “the truth of the matter shows itself, not in some definition or teaching that would conclude philosophical questioning, but rather in the very carrying out of this questioning” (p. 427). If we relate the issue of “pure thinking” to an education that would be consistent with it because it is instantiated by Heidegger’s Socrates, the ever-renewed practice of the dialectic requires, as Gonzalez elucidates, a form of *pure thinking* that is “always underway and yet so in touch with the being of the matter in question as to be continually changed by it,” i.e., a thinking in relation to truth that can never be brought to full unhiddenness and yet still holds the supreme power to transform the soul (*epagoge*), and this thinking “pays more attention to the way,” or practice and movement, of the dialectic, “than to the content without becoming contentless,” or devolving into a transposable, applicable, formable, and hence, empty method, and this type of *pure thinking* “transforms without instructing” (p. 431).

² We undoubtedly get the sense of *απαλλαγη* (*apallage*) referring to the “casting out” of ignorance through dialectic. But this term can also indicate, as we have suggested, in addition to “*deliverance, release, riddance* of a thing,” the “*going away*” or taking a “*departure*” from a thing, hence our reference to truth’s *movement away* from our understanding as well as the *movement away* that we experience from our previous state of ignorance in the midst of the dialectic (Lexicon, p. 76).

of Being, and this movement is highlighted, as in the case of Socrates, by the back-and-forth of the question-rejoinder-refutation of the dialectic in *praxis*—all the while, as Heidegger (1968) claims, there is an attendance to what remains “unspoken” in the dialogue (p. 17), i.e., this highlights our relationship to and encounter with *aletheia*. When learning, as stated, we are inspired, attuned and held fast in wonder (*thauma*) to continually inquire into that which withdraws from full disclosure, “drawn to what withdraws” (p. 17), and in this process, we are located at an ontological distance from the essential nature of what remains *question-worthy*, and hence worthy of our educational pursuits, and here we experience a *way-of-Being* within a context of thinking highlighted by the “mutual nearness of its appeal” (p. 17). So, within this questioning in the midst of this distance from truth, a proximity we can never close off, although *distressing*, we find the inspiration to continue on, for this thinking at a distance is attuned to continue on in the pursuit of what withdraws from our inquiry. In learning, the partial and oblique revelation of truth, or the *intimation of truth*, nourishes the soul and inspires us to hold ourselves in the ever-evolving draft of thinking, for like Socrates, if we are attuned to the “call” of education itself, we do “nothing else than place [ourselves] into this draft, this current, and maintain [ourselves] in it” (p. 17), for it is only in this draft that enlightenment and authentic education can occur.¹

What we have described in this essay, in relation to Socrates and inquiry, might be expressed in Heideggerian terms as the *event* of education that uniquely includes the phenomena of attunement (*Erstaunen*) and *Gelassenheit* occurring with the context of learning. Heidegger (1956) is emphatic that the *pathos* of *Erstaunen* penetrates and pervades the entire philosophical project or process of seeking knowledge—as its *archē*—and so it determines, as we have mentioned, the practitioner’s “dis-position” (p. 83). *Das Erstaunen* facilitates the resolute approach to questioning as described above, a questioning, we recall, that both propels Socrates forward and holds him in the *sway* and *draft* of the inquiry. In this occurrence or *event*, the inquirer is inspired to display, and beyond, instantiate, the attuned attitude of “self-restraint,” which is a *dis-position* in which the inquirer refrains from imposing her prejudices in advance onto to the thing or issue under investigation. Here, Heidegger (1966) has in mind a troubling characteristic of contemporary thinking, let us call it “calculative thought,” associated with a way of knowing grounded and enacted in the willed effort to know and hence “possess” and “appropriate” things in a way that exhausts their Being in knowledge (p. 58). Rather than imposing our will onto that into which we inquire, Heidegger urges us to release ourselves over to it in advance—*Gelassenheit zu den Dingen* (“releasement toward things”)—granting it the space to manifest and reveal itself in its own Being, on its own terms, in its own unique manner of self-showing. In this occurrence, as Heidegger points out, the inquirer stays and remains *released* in inquiry in such a way that she is given over to the thing, and in effect, in an original manner, *belongs to it*, “insofar as [she] is *appropriated* initially” by it, rather than the reverse (p. 73, emphasis in original). In this attuned disposition, to return to Heidegger’s (1956) analysis of *Erstaunen*, there is a “retreat” of that which is questioned from full and complete disclosure, and although, *and indeed because*, the inquirer, under the spell of and in the grip of *Erstaunen*, remains “self-restrained,” she is “forcibly drawn to and, as it were, held fast by that which ... retreats” (p. 85), or, as we have stated, the inquirer is drawn into and secured within the inquiry into that which perpetually withdraws or recedes from full revelation.

¹ For a detailed analysis focused on *Gelassenheit* and education in Heidegger’s later philosophy, which does not reference Socrates, see: Schwieler, E., and Magrini J. (2015). “Meditative Thought and *Gelassenheit* in Heidegger’s Thought of the Turn: Releasing Ourselves to the Original Event of Learning,” *Analysis and Metaphysics*, 14, 7-37.

It is understandable then, why such an event occurs and must occur as the continued “repetition” of the process, which is why, as stated throughout, the event of *originary* learning finds no end, no teleological point of complete closure, no final moment of full enlightenment. For enlightenment, when and if it comes, arrives slowly and only after long and engaged inquiry, granted in the *sway* and *draft* of the unfolding educative process (Plato 1997, *EP VII*; Heidegger 1968).

Returning to and concluding with Socrates, Heidegger (1968) states that as Socrates is drawn into what withdraws, “he points into what withdraws,” and in this way we might think of him as serving as a “sign, a pointer,” but what he is pointing at is “something which has not, not yet, been transposed into the language of our speech” (p. 18); indeed, still to this day, what Socrates philosophized—which he could not properly or systematically bring to language—has not yet been understood by a majority of educators, who are “like those people who run to seek refuge from any draft too strong for them” (p. 17). In the presence of Heidegger’s Socrates, we find ourselves faced with the practice of education that is not only foreign but radically at odds, proximally and for the most part, with the way we as contemporary educators have viewed and practiced education. For education as described relating to and emerging from Heidegger’s Socrates cannot be reduced to the type of method that can be successfully reproduced or imitated in the classroom with the aim of producing the result of learning, which can be gauged through quantification. To even attempt to thematize or systematize it would serve only to bastardize its unique and original essence; indeed, to write it down in the service of a systematized or scripted curriculum, with the requisite set “lesson-plans,” already betrays Heidegger’s point about one of the things that makes Socrates the *purest thinker of the West*, namely, “he wrote nothing,” and if he would have attempted to do so, he would have turned away from authentic thought, or “pure thought,” to become a “fugitive” of thought (pp. 17-18). Thus, a Socratic education drawn from Heidegger’s reading is a form of learning and education which, to continue a theme drawn from contemporary Platonic scholarship, by its very essence must remain non-systematic; it cannot become a *doctrine* in the sense that we in education understand it today. However, it is my hope that this essay might work in service of offering Socratic intimations of and gestures toward—despite how veiled these elucidations must remain—inspiring new and potentially fecund thinking on the ways we currently go about educating our students, offering philosophical insights into the potential re-conceptualization of what we currently understand about the standards for methods, truth, and learning. For the education I have attempted to describe and elucidate, as related to Heidegger’s Socrates, depends on a genuine form of questioning that lies at the heart of the educational experience, where deep transformation and attunement to the soul (*psychē*) or disposition (*hexis*) occurs. Here, it is possible to understand the *pathos-of-education* in Heideggerian (1959) terms as the *event* of “tuning” or the “turning” of the “dis-position and determination” (p. 83), i.e., the soul in *periagoge* turned back to itself enlightened, and it is enlightened in and through a unique and non-systematic understanding of the experience of truth as *aletheia*, in the occurrence of *aletheuein* as it is inseparable from the *originary* context of education, which shelters and facilitates the *draft of authentic thinking and learning*: authentic *paideia*.

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A Free Flow Between Becomings and Becoming Imperceptible— Rare, but Possible

Klas Roth

“[W]e bathe in delirium,” Gilles Deleuze (2001, p. 43) says in *Pure Immanence: Essays on A Life*, asserting that “history presents us with a most peculiar phenomenon: the reactive forces triumph ... [and] Everywhere we see the victory of No over Yes, of reaction over action” (pp. 74-75). And because of this he thinks that “[l]ife becomes adaptive and regulative” (p. 75) and that we no longer understand what it means to become imperceptible, that is, creative—the restless inhabitant of imperceptible becoming. Such insights concerning the darker sides of life, or what he called the overwhelming reactive forces, the sadness of life, which he had developed earlier in his *Nietzsche and Philosophy* (1983a), suggest that he had given up on the hope that the whole human species would make a free flow between perceptible becomings and becoming imperceptible possible. Does this suggest that he gave up the hope that specific individuals can make such a free flow possible in education and society at large? I do not think so. I argue that his writings suggest that a free flow between perceptible becomings and becoming imperceptible is possible, and that this flow requires a recognition of active and reactive forces as well as a regulation of reactive forces through thinking (Deleuze, 1994), something a post-humanist such as Rosi Braidotti does not acknowledge to any great extent. On the contrary, she focuses one-sidedly on the affirmation of active forces, asserting that there is a way out of the reactive; she even claims that it is possible to remove reactive forces. I argue that such a one-sided view is naïve and does not support a free flow between becomings and imperceptible becoming; it misrecognises reactive forces, and leads to a one-sided view of affirmation, joy, and happiness, and to dead-end utopias such as the one suggested by Nathan Snaza and John A. Weaver (2015).

Deleuze, who warns about such tendencies mentioned above, affirmed not merely the value, but also the possibility of and hope for a free flow between becoming perceptible and becoming imperceptible. He also expresses, inter alia, in his latest book, the woeful examples of people becoming slaves through education and in societies by repeating the flow of cases forged by “fictive causal chains, illegitimate rules [and the] simulacra of belief ... [through] simple verbal repetition that only simulates its effect” (Deleuze, 2001, p. 42). Such forces will, according to Deleuze, not merely make any individual or group fall into present concerns and maintain them as if these should be upheld, but will also make people believe that they have to try to solve issues or problems under already more or less given conditions, without necessarily changing these conditions or the way issues and problems are understood. In order to oppose such moves, Deleuze argues for the importance of acting upon our freedom to respond responsibly to chains of constraining conditions through thinking.¹ Such a response is, for him, not about moving beyond

¹ Even though Deleuze portrays, via Friedrich Nietzsche, the historical conditions for freedom in not very positive terms, he is optimistic about the possibility that at least some people can move away from constraining chains, and find their ways anew—themes that we also see cropping up in Hannah Arendt and Immanuel Kant, although in different ways; see also Allen W. Wood (2014), who argues, through Immanuel Kant, Johan Gottlieb Fichte, Karl Marx and Georg Wilhelm

reactive forces or about a transition from becoming perceptible to becoming imperceptible; it is rather about a free flow or play or moving between perceptible becomings and becoming imperceptible. Such moves are, for Deleuze, not easily actualised, at least not in relation to powerful reactive forces such as *ressentiment* and bad conscience, which he thinks diminish the possibility of becoming imperceptible or even triumph over it. Both of these can weigh one down, and make it hard to find one's way again, according to him. For example, *ressentiment* separates the active force from what it can do, that is, from bursting creativity, and, when this is the case, the separation leads, for Deleuze, to an inability to respect and love, to the imputation of wrongs to the other, even to the need to view the other as evil. It can then make those concerned oppose "themselves to active forces and represent themselves as superior" (Deleuze, 1983a, p. 123), and even hide their "hatred under a tempting love: I who accuse you, it is for your own good; I love you in order that you will join me, until you are joined with me, until you yourself become a painful, sick, reactive being, a good being" (1983a, p. 128). A sign of this is when the other has its conscience being poisoned and becomes the slave of its slavishness. *Ressentiment* then becomes a powerful reactive force, together with bad conscience; that is, when, through projection, it has made the other responsible for whatever it is that caused the situation, and the other cries, "It is my fault, it is my fault" (1983a, p. 132). When this happens, *ressentiment* makes one hostile towards the other; it creates a sense of jealousy and of inferiority towards the other, and makes one believe that one's presumed inferiority justifies one's actions towards the other, and that one can do what one wants with the other, instead of engaging in becoming imperceptible and making it possible for the other to do the same. It even fuels shame and guilt on the part of the other; the other can, then, feel so overwhelmed by negative emotions that he/she feels at a loss, even becomes invisible, that is, diminished to the point that he or she loses him- or herself, at times even completely. Reactive forces have then triumphed over active forces.

In my view, shame and guilt can be related not merely to negativity, but also to what could be done in a positive sense, something that Deleuze does not seem to consider.¹ He says, for example, that

Friedrich Hegel, for the free development of each in the various relations they encounter. Hence, as constrained beings, people are not just slaves to present conditions, even though, at times, it is so or may feel so; they are free, or at least capable of acting upon the idea of freedom, in relation to conditions that limit their freedom. So, we see that Deleuze is in good company when it comes to acknowledging constraining conditions, while at the same time recognizing the value of freedom, even though he does so in a somewhat different way than, inter alia, Arendt and Kant.

¹ Stanley Cavell, for example, views shame and guilt not merely in relation to disgust or disdain, but also as "a call for a transformation of things, and before all a transformation of the self" (1990, p. 46); the latter is, as I argue, through the voice of Cavell, "a return to philosophy" (Roth, 2010, p. 396), and to the possibility of finding one's way again. See also Kant (1996) when he says that conscience is the "*internal court* in man ('before which his thoughts accuse or excuse one another')" (p. 203/AA 6: p. 438) (here and elsewhere in this article, references to Kant cite page numbers from the English translation followed by volume and page number from the German *Akademie-Ausgabe* edition of Kant's works. "Translations of Kant's works commonly include volume and page numbers of the Academy Edition. References to the Academy Edition often use 'AA' for *Akademie-Ausgabe*" ["Further Reading," in Kant 2017, p. xxxii]). Here Kant treats conscience as a crucial aspect of our duty to engage in self-examination and self-knowledge. It should remind us of our duty to engage in the pursuit of coming to "*know* (scrutinize, fathom)

humanity's "only hope lies in a revolutionary becoming: the only way of casting off ... shame or responding to what is intolerable" (1995, p. 171). Here we see that, even though Deleuze seems to say that shame is potentially productive, it is more a question of a casting of shame than of being reminded of what can be done through shame in a constructive sense.¹ That is, if one lets shame weigh oneself down, then it is not constructive, but if, for example, shame is related to what one could do, that is, to becoming imperceptible, then it does not weigh one down. It becomes, instead, an active force. Nonetheless, even though Deleuze does not seem to recognise that conscience can work both ways, he is clear about the dangers of not encountering the above-mentioned forces responsibly through thinking, and of believing that there is a way out of reactive forces. Such thoughts open up, for Deleuze, not merely to a disintegration of the various possible becomings, but also to fictional ideas such as dead-end utopias. He also thinks that these ideas open the door to reactive forces that diminish our freedom to find our way again.² It is therefore risky, even dangerous, that a post-humanist such as Braidotti, who draws on the work of Deleuze, focuses so one-sidedly on the affirmation of various becomings, joy and the vital force of life—Zoe—without paying enough attention to the value of also encountering and regulating reactive forces, which Deleuze, through Friedrich Nietzsche, emphasises.³ Even though she says that she wants to

yourself" (Kant, 2017, p. 206/AA 6: p. 441). Hence, Kant treats conscience as a morally motivating feeling, leading either to negativity or to positivity, that is, either to a feeling that weighs one down or to a feeling that awakens one to one's responsibility to find one's way again or, in Kant's own words, to a moral feeling that awakens one's duty to improve oneself morally. Conscience, for Kant, is therefore not necessarily bad; it can be seen also as a reminder of our duty to do what the moral law requires, even demands, of us.

¹ Aislinn O'Donnell (2017), for example, defends a view of shame in the writings of Deleuze that focuses more on casting shame off, instead of viewing it as a force that also can be understood as a reminder of what can be done in a more positive sense. Even Sjoerd van Tuinen (2014), who talks about Deleuze's writings on shame and guilt, does not draw attention to how shame and guilt can be a call for transformation and/or a reminder of our duty to scrutinize ourselves.

² See Deleuze (2001), and his book on Nietzsche and his philosophy (1983a, in particular Chapters 2 and 4), in which he continuously comes back to the idea that reactive forces triumph over the active; in this book, Deleuze (1983a) also argues that "an active force *becomes reactive* (in a new sense) when reactive forces (in the first sense) separate it from what it can do" (p. 57). When this happens, an active force is "dragged into the abyss and turned against itself" (Deleuze, 1983a, p. 67), thereby hindering it to "produce a burst of creativity" (Deleuze, 1983a, p. 111). However, it is not just a case of an active force being separated from what it can do; it is also dangerous to offer more or less easy ways out of reactive forces, since doing so misrecognises the strength of reactive forces, thereby contaminating the active.

³ See for example, Braidotti (2006; 2011; 2018; 2019), in which she somewhat surprisingly focuses merely on affirming the vital force of Zoe, but not on finding a balance between active and reactive forces in a developed sense. It is also surprising that Ian Buchanan, in edited books such as *A Deleuzian Century?* (1999) and *Deleuze and the Contemporary World* (2006), edited together with Adrian Parr, does not draw attention to Deleuze's call for encountering both active and reactive forces. Sjoerd van Tuinen (2014), however, draws some attention to active and reactive forces, and to the reactive triumphing over the active. Unfortunately, Van Tuinen (2014) merely mentions

replace what she calls the negativity of reactive forces with “Spinoza’s ethics of joyful affirmation” (2013, p. 343), without dismissing “the reality of conflict and pain” (2019, p. 154), she does not encounter reactive forces thoroughly, nor how these can be regulated. On the contrary, she says, naively, that “the pursuit of an ethics of joyful affirmation” (2019, p. 72) not only takes the “negative elements ... seriously” (2019, p. 154), but also removes “the barriers of negativity” (2018, p. 221) and “offers a way out of the state of exhaustion, anxiety and fear” (2019, p. 154), not merely at a particular time, but eternally.

Hence, even though it seems that she would not want to dismiss reactive forces, she also asserts that there is a way out of them, and that they can be removed, and stopped from having a negative impact on ourselves. Such a one-sided and blind emphasis on “an ethics of joyful affirmation,” with its stress on “a way out” and on “removing” reactive forces, misrecognises the strength of such forces. As such it opens the gates to dark waters such as fictional utopian ideals of a coming perfect world in which human beings are supposed to experience the fruits of becomings, such as the ones expressed by Braidotti, in terms of affirmation, joy and happiness. The naïve stress on the above-mentioned ethics has even led educational post-humanists such as Snaza and Weaver (2015) to express not merely their wish or hope, but also the promise that posthumanism—with its one-sided emphasis on joyful affirmation—will provide us with “a general direction for an evolutionary development of culture” (p. xi), one that will take us back to the Garden of Eden.¹

the importance of the “becoming-active of the reactive forces that have constituted us, the transmutation of our inherited sentiments such as *ressentiment* and bad conscience” (p. 98), without tackling the idea of striving to find a balance between active and reactive forces through thinking. Finding such a balance is, however, not an easy matter. There is also a certain degree of indeterminacy in deciding on it, despite all available evidence, due to, inter alia, the inscrutability of reference, that is, that words and objects/actions can be connected in various ways, and that we cannot know in each and every case—with certainty—which way is right (see, for example, Donald Davidson [1997] for a discussion on such matters). Moreover, as Paul Guyer (2020) writes, “there is nothing that can guarantee that a free will is always a good will, so nothing that can guarantee that even the most carefully chosen leaders [nor anyone else] will do the right thing.” And he continues, “Even the best institutions only make justice possible, not necessary—the human will can pervert anything” (p. 334). Additionally, people can also deceive the other or themselves that they are trying to find, for example, a balance somewhere in the middle between active and reactive forces, while they in fact are not (see, for example, Donald Davidson [2004], Eric Funkhouser [2019], Clancy Martin [2009] and Laura Papish [2018] for discussions on deception and self-deception). Nonetheless, despite all concerns, it is still of value to pursue or at least to strive to pursue a balance between active and reactive forces, since the opposite is not a reasonable option; it suggests that one give up one’s indefinite individuality of life, to use Deleuze’s words.

¹ Although such images may be appealing, experience shows us that the whole human species has not come back to the Garden of Eden. Moreover, as Moses Mendelssohn (1983) says, “you will find no steady progress in ... [the] development [of the human species] that brings it ever closer to perfection,” nor back to the promised land; despite the lack of such experiences, it happens, according to him, that “a dot blazes up in the midst of the great mass, [and] becomes a glittering star” (pp. 96-97). Such insights by Mendelssohn are, unfortunately, not reflected in the work by Snaza and Weaver, nor in the work by Braidotti. Moreover, even though some human beings can

None of them, therefore, undertakes the task of regulating reactive forces through thinking.¹ It is therefore problematic that the above-mentioned authors focus so narrowly on just one of two forces which are, for Deleuze, inseparable. Deleuze also argues that the denial of the vital balance between the above forces drags us down into the abyss of evaluating others and ourselves in relation to the extent to which we pursue various specific ends such as the dead-end utopias mentioned above, with their one-sided stress on affirmation and joy. It is, for him, not a simple case of experiencing joy when moving between various becomings. Such moves can also fuel frustration, anxiety, fear, despair and loss. It is not even the case that moves between perceptible and imperceptible becomings necessarily lead to an experience of happiness; such moves can be overwhelming and terrifying, and lead to disorder and chaos, apart from transformations over time; this can be seen in science, philosophy and art as well as in other ways of life, in particular when people come up with something new and original which may constitute an example of a work of genius.² People can respond in negative ways to that which stands as an example of originality, and it can take years before such a work is recognised as original; this is due to the fact that people do not necessarily and in each and every case want to disturb and destabilise that what they believe, which when it happens can frustrate and even lead to loss and despair; it may even be the case that they avoid opening the gates to territories unknown to them, for fear of doing so. Their responses can, therefore, be an expression of reactive forces in relation to that which at some point can be recognised as original and as an example of genius. Additionally, it is not clear whether Braidotti thinks that her suggested path to the affirmation of joy necessarily concerns the whole human species or all species as such, or whether it concerns what Deleuze called the indefinite individuality of life. Nor is it clear whether Braidotti thinks that there is a sure way of arousing and maintaining an ethics of joyful affirmation over time, a becoming which Deleuze (1995) does not think is possible to arouse or maintain consistently over time; such issues ought to be clarified.

Apart from what has been said above, Deleuze also thinks that a misrecognition of the power of reactive forces has led to more or less modern philosophical and fictional ideas concerning, *inter alia*, the possibility for human beings to render themselves autonomous in each and every situation

become “glittering stars,” there is no guarantee that they will continue to be such creatures. On the contrary, human beings can oscillate between active and reactive forces and backslide—even wilfully—from the pursuit of an ethics of joyful affirmation (see also note 3, p. 112 above).

¹ Donna Haraway (2016), for example, also points out the dangers of not staying with specific troubles. She argues that when one does not do so, one can be led to either utopian (or dystopian) thoughts (as in the case of Snaza and Weaver), or to naïve views of finding a way out of reactive forces (as in the case of Braidotti).

² See Deleuze and Guattari (1994), in particular their final chapter “Conclusion: From Chaos to the Brain,” in which they argue that neither art, science, nor philosophy can avoid chaos completely; these faculties can, however, “return from the land of the dead” (p. 202) by creating something new and original. Hence, even though Braidotti seems to think that she can avoid chaos entirely by offering a way to joy and happiness, it is, for Deleuze and Guattari, not possible to avoid chaos, other than temporarily, and through hard and creative work.

through the use of their understanding and reason, something that Deleuze disputes.¹ He thinks that we cannot control reactive forces effectively. A reason for this is, for Deleuze, that the unconscious and constitutive synthesis of habits is so strong that we cannot control reactive forces completely.² Another reason is that Deleuze together with Guattari believes that the above-mentioned formation of habits is shaped and disciplined under the conditions of the capitalist market.³ They think this market shapes and controls our images and directs our desire towards them instead of encouraging a free flow between perceptible and imperceptible becoming. Deleuze (1994) thinks, therefore, that it is just a fiction that we can control our actions effectively in each and every situation. Such a disconcerting view does not, however, suggest, for him, that we are slaves under the above-mentioned conditions. On the contrary, he believes that we can react and respond responsibly to flows of habitual reactive behaviour through thinking, and this we can do, according to him, by increasing our powers of thinking by affirming such a good mode

¹ Deleuze criticizes Kant's ideas of autonomy. He thinks that Kant does not pay enough attention to challenges people encounter when they try to render themselves autonomous. Kant, however, was aware of the challenges that human beings face when they try to render themselves autonomous; see, for example, his *Religion within the Boundaries of Mere Reason* (1998b), in which he discusses human beings' innate propensity to radical evil; this is a book Deleuze did not pay much attention to. In it, Kant (1998b) argues that it is hard work to regulate what he called our innate propensity to radical evil, and that it would require "a *revolution* in the disposition of the human being ... so a 'new man' can come about only through a kind of rebirth, as it were a new creation" (p. 68/AA 6: p. 47). Although Kant (1986b) thinks it would require such a revolution, he raises the question whether such a new man ever could come about. He says: "[I]f a human being is corrupt in the very ground of his maxims, how can he possibly bring about this revolution by his own forces and become a good human being on his own?" (p. 68/AA 6: p. 47). He seeks to resolve these seemingly incompatible views about human beings in his *Religion within the Boundaries of Mere Reason*, namely the views that they can and should render themselves autonomous, on the one hand, and that they have an innate propensity to radical evil, which corrupts their duty to render themselves autonomous, on the other. Kant's way of resolving the issue with above-mentioned views is to turn to religion, in particular Christianity. He argues that human beings have to turn to Christianity in order to fulfill their duty to comply with the moral law, since they cannot expect to fulfill their duty on their own, due to their innate propensity to radical evil. Moses Mendelssohn, however, questioned whether Christianity is the only organized religion that can serve as a vehicle for good; see also Paul Guyer (2020) for a discussion on this and similar issues. Whether Kant succeeds in solving the above-mentioned and seemingly incompatible views is also philosophically questionable; see Stephen R. Palmquist (2016, in particular Parts III and IV), Lawrence R. Pasternack (2014, in particular Chapters 5 and 6) and Allen W. Wood (1999, in particular Chapter 9, and 1970, in particular Chapters 5 and 6), for discussions on Kant's views on human beings' duty to render themselves autonomous, and on evil, religion and the Church; also, on whether Kant succeeds in solving the seemingly incompatible views about human beings.

² Our consciousness is for Deleuze a slave of the unconsciousness; in this he is echoing the words of David Hume (1978, p. 415), who argued that reason is the slave of our passions.

³ See Deleuze and Guattari (1987; 2013).

of existence.¹ When we do so, there is, for him, an opening for “an impersonal and yet singular life that releases a pure event freed from the accidents of internal and external life” (Deleuze, 2001, p. 28). Such an opening instantiates an affirmation of a vital form of life, namely the “singularization: a life of pure immanence” (2001, p. 29), which, for him, also opens the door to joy and not to sadness, and to the possibility of becoming new anew. It signifies, moreover, a responsible response towards reactive behaviour (at least for the moment), and “a liberation of thought from those images which imprison it” (Deleuze, 1994, p. xv), that is, from dogmatic thought. It also exemplifies the value of the freedom of moving between different perceptible becomings such as becoming woman, mother, friend, doctor etc., as well as between perceptible becoming *and* becoming imperceptible in an affirmative and joyful dance, in which the active forces are affirmed and the power of the reactive ones are regulated through thinking.² Such a world in which thinking is recaptured marks, for Deleuze, a good mode of existence, in which the process of thinking is open-ended and never-ending; it is a regulative ideal toward which we can move while not fully attaining it.³

The above-mentioned doubleness of becoming suggests, however, that it is not merely moves between already perceptible identities, but also consists of flights that go beyond those more or less fixed identities to that which is not yet, to an affirmation of an infinite flow of newness.⁴ Such moves instantiate flights beyond perceptible becomings to that which is yet to come, to something new. Such a becoming is not, for Deleuze and Guattari (1987), a “correspondence between relations... [nor] is it a resemblance, an imitation, or, at the limit, an identification” (p. 237). It is neither a “progress or regress along a series ..., [it does not] occur in the imagination ... [and it is]

¹ See, for example, Deleuze (1983b, pp. 22-25). Kant (1988b) also thinks that it is a continuous challenge for people to regulate their inclinations and raise themselves above constraining conditions; see also Guyer (2009) for a discussion on this and similar issues.

² See Arendt (2003) and Kant (2000, pp. 174-175/AA 5: p. 294; 2006, pp. 122-124/AA § 59 [7: pp. 226-229]; 2007, pp. 445-446/AA 9: p. 451) for similar arguments concerning the value of thinking; see also for Arendt (2006; 1968, in particular Chapters 12 and 13), and Kant (1998b) for discussions on what can happen when people do not think for themselves, etc. This tendency not to think for oneself cannot merely lead to dogmatic thought, as Deleuze claims, or to totalitarianism in power, as Arendt claims; it can also fuel the three grades of evil, as Kant would claim, namely, the frailty of our will, our liability to deceive others and ourselves, and our capacity to exterminate the other, none of which promotes thinking for oneself or from the standpoint of the other; and it happens constantly. See also Klas Roth (2018; 2019) for discussions that education, as it stands, does not necessarily promote thinking in the-above mentioned Kantian sense.

³ See also Guyer (2014), which argues that Cavell and Kant argue for a similar position, namely that thinking in moral education is never-ending and never ended; see also Roth (2014) for a related standpoint about the process of education.

⁴ See also Kant (2006) which claims that “what can be made of the human being [and] what he is prepared to make of himself” (p. 185/[AA 7: p. 285]) is dependent upon whether he acts upon the idea of freedom or not, which indicates something similar to what Deleuze expresses, namely, that what human beings can become is dependent upon what they are prepared to become through freedom in education and society at large.

not an evolution, at least not an evolution by descent and filiation” (p. 238). It means, for Deleuze (2007a), “never to imitate, nor to ‘do like’, nor to conform to a model, whether it’s of justice or of truth,” and he continues, “There is no terminus from which you set out, none which you arrive at or which you ought to arrive at” (p. 2). Becomings are, for him, therefore “not phenomena of imitation or assimilation, but of a double capture...” (p. 2). This doubleness suggests, moreover, that it is not just a case of moving between various perceptible becomings without becoming imperceptible, since such a one-sided view of becoming diminishes the freedom to engage in thinking and leads to wandering in deserts of illusions such as those expressed by Snaza and Weaver. If, however, people do try to find a balance between the above-mentioned becomings, then it is also possible to move beyond perceptible becomings and engage in lines of flight that have “no beginning or end” (Deleuze, 2007a, p. 30). Such flights are for him, therefore, not a part

of history; [since] history amounts only the set of preconditions, however recent, that one leaves behind in order to “become,” that is, to create something new. (Deleuze, 1995, p. 171)

Such flights are, for him, creative, and societies that make it possible for those concerned to encounter them are characterised not so much by their reactive forces, nor by their contradictions, but by their flights to horizons, something Deleuze believes happens in philosophy, literature, and science when the free flow between the doubleness of becoming is made possible.¹ However, the free flow or dance implies, for Deleuze and Guattari (1994), not merely a movement between perceptible becomings and imperceptible becoming, but it also implies the inevitability of chaos, a chaos that “undoes every consistency in the infinite” (p. 42), which can be a difficult experience. This is because it is a move away from ourselves, our specific identities, and when this happens, we find ourselves wandering in deserts “populated by tribes, flora and fauna” (Deleuze, 2007b, p. 11), and sometimes in despair before we can find our way again and become filled with hope for the possibility of flights beyond that which is already known to that which has no beginning nor end. However, as we have seen, even though Deleuze in some of his earlier writings may have had the hope that such societies could come about, he became more doubtful, perhaps even more despondent, in his hope for the possibility that the whole human species could become imperceptible. Some of Deleuze’s darker views can, however, also be seen earlier on, as when he talks about control societies, and says

People are of course constantly talking about prisons, schools, hospitals: the institutions are breaking down. But they’re breaking down because they’re fighting a losing battle. New kinds of punishment, education, health care are being stealthily introduced. (Deleuze, 1995, pp. 174-175)

Or when he says

Educational reforms, industrial reforms, hospital, army, prison reforms ... everyone knows these institutions are in more or less terminal decline. It’s simply a matter of nursing them through their death throes and keeping people busy until the new forces

¹ See Deleuze (1995, p. 171), and also Deleuze (2007b), in which he argues that “philosophy is a discipline that is just as inventive, just as creative as any other discipline, and it consists in creating or inventing concepts” (p. 318).

knocking at the door take over. (Deleuze, 1995, p. 178)

The passages above seem to suggest that even though there are examples of what he calls becoming imperceptible or lines of flight in societies, Deleuze came to believe that it is a lost battle for the whole human species, something Braidotti does not seem to believe in with her emphasis on a way out of reactive forces. This is so not merely because people get caught in reactive behaviour and more or less troublesome separations between active and reactive forces, but also because of all that which, according to Deleuze and Guattari (1994), threatens thinking, such as “stupidity, forgetfulness, aphasia, delirium, madness” (p. 52). Deleuze and Guattari also think that “thought [can be] threatened less by error than by [the] inevitable illusions that come from within reason” (p. 52), something Deleuze thinks Immanuel Kant eloquently has shown in his three critiques.¹ Another reason for this doubt is the lack of examples of becoming imperceptible when it comes to the whole human species. However, and as seen from the above, Deleuze believes that even though there are rare flights of becoming imperceptible, these are not overwhelming or strong enough to combat reactive forces as such. Hence, Deleuze seems to have given up on the belief that the human species as a whole can become imperceptible. He also believes that we do not even have a “sure way of maintaining becomings, or still more of arousing them, even within ourselves” (Deleuze, 1995, p. 173);² this is because we cannot know with certainty how to go on in each and every situation, according to Deleuze (Deleuze, 1983a, p. 58); it is more a question of engaging in the difficult art of thinking. Nonetheless, such dark views about the whole human species’ potential for becoming imperceptible do not suggest that he had given up on the possibility of examples of creativity, of becoming imperceptible, for specific individuals.³ On the contrary. It

¹ See Deleuze (2008), in which he discusses the three critiques of Kant, namely *Critique of the Power of Judgment* (2000); *Critique of Pure Reason* (1998a); *Critique of Practical Reason* (1997); see also Craig Lundy and Daniela Voss (2015, in particular Chapters 1-4) for critical discussions on Deleuze interpretation of Kant’s philosophy as it is expressed in his three critiques.

² See also Kant (1998b), who argued that “the depths of his own heart (the subjective first ground of his maxims) are to him inscrutable” (p. 71/AA 6: p. 51). People cannot, therefore, be certain of how to comply with the moral law, nor how they can maintain it. See also Kant’s comments on ends that are also duties in his *Metaphysics of Morals* (2017, pp. 160-170/AA, 6: pp. 386-6: 398), namely on our duties to perfect ourselves and the happiness of others, which for Kant, are wide, and therefore do not specify how or when to perfect ourselves and make others happy. Kant says, for example, that no “rational principle prescribes specifically *how* far one should go in cultivating one’s capacities (in enlarging or correcting one’s capacity for understanding, i.e., in acquiring knowledge or skill)” (Kant, 2017, p.165/AA 6: p. 392), nor does such a principle prescribe specifically how one can go about helping others to become happy. Additionally, the fulfillment of such principles is, for Kant, meritorious, “but failure to fulfill them is not in itself *culpability*” (Kant, 2017, p. 164/AA, 6: p. 390).

³ The question, however, about whether the whole of humankind or individuals are progressing is not new. It was also discussed between Moses Mendelssohn and Immanuel Kant, where Mendelssohn (1983) says, “Now, as far as human race as a whole is concerned, you will find no steady progress in its development that brings it ever closer to perfection. Rather do we see the human race in its totality slightly oscillate; it never took a few steps forward without soon afterwards, and with redoubled speed, sliding back to its previous position.... Individual man

would not merely be a contradiction to claim that there are no such examples and have never been; it would also suggest a lack of recognition and understanding of the obvious examples of creativity in, for example, philosophy, science and art. But this is not what Deleuze expresses. It is rather the other way around. He continuously comes back to the possibility of becoming imperceptible by using examples from philosophy, science and art in education and society at large, and by encouraging thinking. He says, for example,

The task of philosophy when it creates concepts, entities, is always to extract an event from things and beings, to set up the new event from things and beings, always to give them a new event: space, time, matter, thought, the possible as events. (Deleuze and Guattari, 1994, p. 33)

The creation of concepts can then disturb that which is already known and challenge our ways of understanding.¹ Such events can create cracks in that which is known, and throw us into unknown

advances, but mankind continually fluctuates within fixed limits, while maintaining, on the whole, about the same degree of morality in all periods—the same amount of religion and irreligion, of virtue and vice, of felicity and misery; the same result, if one compares like with like; of all these goods and evils as much as is required for the passage of the individual man in order that he might be educated here below, and approach as closely as possible the perfection which is apportioned to him and for which he is destined” (pp. 96-97). Here we see that Mendelssohn was not optimistic about the progression of humankind. Kant (1991), on the other, and against Mendelssohn, asserts that he (Kant) is “permitted to assume that, since the human race is constantly progressing in cultural matters (in keeping with its natural purpose), it is also engaged in progressive improvement in relation to the moral end of its existence. This progress may at times be *interrupted* but never *broken off*.” And he continues, somewhat surprisingly, “I do not need to prove this assumption; it is up to the adversary to prove his case” (p. 88). The discussion between Mendelssohn and Kant had, however, to do with whether Christianity is a more progressive religion than Judaism and whether Christianity would bring “its adherents closer to moral perfection and should be universally adopted for that reason” (Guyer, 2020, p. 324). Kant, who believed that Christianity is the religion that would bring its adherents closer to perfection, did not believe that Judaism would do so. Mendelssohn, by contrast, thought that perfection is possible for individuals, but not for the whole human species, and believed “that the moral truths of the religion of reason always are and always have been available to all people, thus that Christianity should not be regarded as a more progressive religion than Judaism” (Guyer, 2020, p. 324).

¹ See for example Kant (2000), § 9, pp. 102-105/AA 5: pp. 216-219; § 29, pp. 148-160/AA 5: pp. 264-279; § 50, pp. 196-197/AA 5: 319-321, who argues for the value of searching for new ways of thinking, and claims that this can be done by engaging in the free play between imagination and understanding; see also Guyer (2006) for a discussion on various interpretations of such free play, and for his arguments for how it reasonably should be understood. Guyer also argues that we cannot know how to awaken nor sustain such a free play, nor how we can make ourselves creative in a decisive way; he says, “the very concept of the harmony of the faculties as the explanation of our pleasure in beauty requires that our experience of beauty not be constrained by any determinate rules, such characterizations can never offer anything more than some examples of the ways in which our experience of beauty can go beyond the determinate requirements of cognition” (2006, p. 193).

territories, which can disintegrate us, and hence frustrate and create anxiety, even despair.¹ However infrequent, these are tokens of potentials, which, according to Deleuze, should not be ignored, but taken seriously. He thinks that the potential of such tokens demands of us to make perceptible becomings imperceptible, that is, lines of flight toward the indefinite and infinite. Such engagement is, for Deleuze and Guattari (1994), not disconnected and disengaged. It is instead connected with that which is already known, which is maintained, reproduced, imitated, and copied in an endless process of repetitive acts. It is an encounter with that which is known, with the urgency of impossible situations, in which questions of immediacy require acts of thinking other than the ones expected; such events are, for Deleuze (2015) “actualized in us, they wait for us and invite us in” (p.153). He believes that such acts can break with that which is already known—from dogmatic images of thought, dead-end utopias, and naïve affirmations of joy and happiness. He also thinks that the singularisation of such acts deterritorialise us and others, and open the door to the possibility of finding one’s way again, a process seemingly open to each and every one at any time. It enlarges thought beyond that which is known to the horizon of the possible, to new possibilities that are not, and cannot be, known in advance, nor aroused in accordance with specific guidelines or rules. To think new thoughts is, therefore, for Deleuze and Guattari (1994), to engage in experimenting with that which is actual, the shapes, lines, colours, moves that are already in place. It is to destabilise them. It is to move in unforeseen ways, not necessarily limited by present and historical states. It is to actualise that which is not and cannot be known beforehand; it is, for Deleuze, to become “someone who creates [his or her] own impossibilities, and thereby creates possibilities” without which we would not “have the line of flight, the exit that is creation” (Deleuze, 1995, p. 133). To think is therefore “to create—there is no other creation—but to create is first of all to engender ‘thinking’ in thought” (Deleuze, 1994, p. 185). Without thinking we are lost, reduced to objects of destructive forces, which limit, even triumph over us and our possibilities. Without thinking we give in to circumstances that make us slaves or move us in misleading directions. We give up the originality of thought, and diminish our ability to be creative and to engage “in new, perhaps previously unimagined, modes of thinking” (Jeanes, 2006, p. 128). In order to combat such destructive forces, we should, engage in thinking, which is territorial, that is, placed in various moves or ways of life; thinking leads us to encounter both active and reactive forces, which for Deleuze, is a “fundamental *encounter*” (Deleuze, 1994, p. 176), one which can deterritorialise us in relation to the various embedded ways of thought and fuel the “passion to think” (p. 176), and as such can open the possibility to recapture that which is lost, and help us to find our way anew.

Thinking is, therefore, always dangerous. It means, for Deleuze and Guattari (1994), “to follow the witch’s flight” (p. 41) and move from that which is known to the unthought. It leads us to experiment without predetermined or fixed ends, and is as such “an art of living” (Deleuze, 1995, p. 111). To move between perceptible becomings and becoming imperceptible through thinking is therefore to “head for the horizon, on the plane of immanence, and ... [to] return with bloodshot eyes, yet they are the eyes of the mind” (Deleuze and Guattari, 1994, p. 41). It leads us to “cross the line, and make it endurable, workable, thinkable” (Deleuze, 1995, p. 111). Such thinking is a real possibility, although sometimes it is overwhelmed, even triumphed over, by reactive forces.

¹ See Fredrika Spindler (2011) for a discussion on Deleuze and the event, and on how events can create cracks in that which is known so that lines of flight can be created to that which is not yet known.

It can lead us away from a narrow focus on active forces, the one-sided views on affirmation, joy and happiness and dead-end utopias, to an encounter with both active and reactive forces, the impact of capitalism on the formation of our images, as well as to a real affirmation of the indefinite individuality of life, which when it happens is hard work.

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The Relationship Between Common Sense and Thinking: Keeping with the Event in Education

Ingrid Andersson

Introduction

In this article, I investigate the relationship between common sense and thinking. Two prominent philosophers of our Western tradition that have problematized the notions of common sense and thinking from different yet similar perspectives are Gilles Deleuze and Hannah Arendt. Common sense and thinking are both to be understood in juxtaposition to the notion of the *event*. The event is something that happens to us from the outside, while at the same time it is captured in our linguistic expressions, yet not contained within them.

The article is organized as follows. The first section accounts for the philosophy of Gilles Deleuze and his views on thinking, sense and the event. Although his concepts are manifold and connect with one another in multiple ways, I have restricted myself to keeping with the concepts noted above. Additional concepts such as virtual intensities will be embedded in my discussion as an element of the aforementioned concepts and not as free-standing ones (although none of his concepts are free-standing). Following that, I account for Hannah Arendt's philosophy based on my reading of *The Human Condition* and *The Life of the Mind*, by addressing her notions of thinking, judging and common sense. In the third section, I show how Deleuze and Arendt can be read through one another by directing my attention to their respective takes on common sense. I conclude my paper with a discussion of how common sense and thinking, read through Deleuze and Arendt, have implications for education.

Images of Thinking

In *Difference and Repetition* (2014), we come across Deleuze's "image of thought." Images of thought are the philosophical presuppositions that have permeated Western philosophical thinking dating back to Plato. The images of thought ground thinking and steer it in a certain direction in that presuppositions are not called into question. For instance, the Cartesian image of thought captured by the *cogito* presupposes "that everybody knows what it means to think" (Deleuze, 2014). It presupposes a subject *detached* from the world, the object, which the subject can strive to get to know (Colebrook, 2001).

This Cartesian image, Deleuze explains, contains three levels: a naturally upright thought, an in-principle natural common sense, and a transcendental model of recognition (2014, p. 177). These assumptions, Deleuze claims, are pre-philosophical since they constitute the inner condition for thinking without being subjected to scrutiny themselves. We are not actually thinking with this image in place; we are merely recognizing. The "I think" is presupposed to be the unifier of all

our faculties, and the *cogito* becomes the philosophical concept of common sense. For Deleuze, true thought is “primarily trespass and violence, the enemy, and nothing presupposes philosophy: everything begins with misosophy” (2014, p. 183). What forces us to think is an object of an encounter, not recognition, and its primary characteristic is that it can only be *sensed*. From the perspective of recognition, it is imperceptible.

What Deleuze seeks to liberate is “pure difference.” Pure difference is difference *in itself* and cannot as such be reduced to the separative nature of habitual thought and recognition in which difference gains its tenor through comparison. For instance, when we say, “Lars is different from Laila,” we merely erect a fence between them, routinely grafted on current cultural understandings, for example gender, in which the difference of Lars is completely dependent on the identity of Laila. Within common-sense understanding, with rigid and solidified analytical categories (for instance man/woman), we lose the two-fold sense of pure difference: firstly, difference as *transfiguration*; and secondly, difference as *immanent within the actual* (Bogue, 2004).

The Immanent Event

Deleuze draws a line between morality and ethics. Morality, Deleuze claims, is rooted in a representational image of thought (Spangenberg, 2009, p. 90). This representational image presupposes who we are and what we ought to do, rather than what we have the potential to become. What hinders us from exceeding who we are, and becoming something different, is identity and habitual thinking. Deleuze holds the view that when we identify, we represent, and when we represent, we remove ourselves from the potentiality of becoming imperceptible. Identity in representation prevents us from experiencing the virtual intensities of pure difference. To enable thinking, and to counteract recognition, Deleuze introduces his notion of Ideas with a capital ‘I’ to distinguish his understanding of Ideas from our common usage of ideas as contained in our minds (Spangenberg, 2009, p. 94). Ideas and problems constitute the transcendental conditions for thought for Deleuze. In the *Logic of Sense* (2015), sense is understood as identical with the event (Deleuze, 1990). Since Ideas reside in the virtual realm, they can only be sensed and not contained within a representational scheme. For Deleuze, sensations and virtual intensities “are the virtual but necessary conditions for the occurrence of significant events” (Spangenberg, 2009, p. 94). Events, Deleuze continues, are incorporeal entities that are expressed through language yet subsist beyond their manifestation. Concepts, in that they are created as a response (not a solution) to particular problems, are an example of events.

Thus, what is expressed in a proposition, the sense/event, is distinguished from the bodies it denotes. In this way, the virtual and the actual are interconnected yet belong to different orders. Common sense for Deleuze is always representational and hence dogmatic and moral. We need to be ethically attuned to the event to actualize pure thought. In Spangenberg’s words, “Deleuze conceives of ethics as an event and as inextricably linked with the sole aim of philosophy: to become imperceptible or, as Deleuze would also say, to become worthy of the event” (2009, p. 90). And how do we do that?

To be worthy of the event, we need to extract the virtual event from a state of affairs. This move Deleuze calls a “counter-actualization.” For example, say one has an unusual experience while reading a novel. The particular novel elicits new and uncommon sensations in the reader. Perhaps

the narrator in the story presents a perceptual field that seems completely alien to the reader. This experience is first and foremost *sensed* rather than comprehended, Deleuze would claim, in that the encounter with this new way of perceiving is not eligible for representation and identification: the sensation, encounter, forces us to think *involuntarily*. This encounter with something new and different ignites an idea constitutive of a problem that actualizes thinking in that we are forced to explicate something of which there exists no pre-given representation. In other words, we experience difference as transfiguration and immanent within the actual. Now, a counter-actualization would be to immerse oneself in that creative flow unleashed by the new encounter, to be transformed, and bring that process of transformation into new situations.

The Creation of Concepts

In *What is Philosophy?* (2014), Deleuze, and Guattari present their view on immanence, or more precisely “the plane of immanence.” Philosophy, they contend, is constructivism with the purpose of creating concepts and laying out a plane of immanence. The plane is presupposed in that concepts refer to a non-conceptual understanding. If philosophy involves the creation of concepts, then the plane is the ground for the creation itself. However, this does not mean that the pre-philosophical is outside of philosophy or that it precedes it, although it is pre-supposed by philosophy:

Philosophy is at once concept creation and instituting of the plane. The concept is the beginning of philosophy, but the plane is its instituting. The plane is clearly not a program, design, end, or means: it is a plane of immanence that constitutes the absolute ground of philosophy, its earth or deterritorialization, the foundation on which it creates its concepts. Both the creation of concepts and the instituting of the plane are required, like two wings or fins. (p. 41)

The plane of immanence *is* the image of thought: “The plane of immanence is not a concept that is or can be thought but rather the image of thought, the image thought gives itself of what it means to think, to make use of thought, to find one’s bearings in thought” (p. 41). Important to note is that the plane of immanence is not a concept in itself since a concept is always a response to a problem and hence cannot constitute a foundation. The image of thought is thus no longer dogmatic, since it is now a movable plane, not a re-presentation. With the plane of immanence, Deleuze and Guattari understand an infinite yet absolute horizon from which thinking is given consistency:

Concepts are concrete assemblages, like the configurations of a machine, but the plane is the abstract machine of which these assemblages are the working parts. Concepts are events, but the plane is the horizon of events, the reservoir or reserve of purely conceptual events: not the relative horizon that functions as a limit, which changes with an observer and encloses observable states of affairs, but the absolute horizon, independent of any observer, which makes the event as concept independent of a visible state of affairs in which it is brought about. (Guattari and Deleuze, 2014, p. 36)

The image of thought, Deleuze and Guattari explain, “implies a strict division between fact and *right*.” Thus, historical facts or facts pertaining to the function of the brain are contingent and must therefore be separated from thought as such: “The image of thought retains only what thought can claim by right. Thought demands ‘only’ movement that can be carried to infinity. What thought claims by right, what it selects, is infinite movement or the movement of the infinite. It is this that constitutes the image of thought” (2014, p. 37). Immanence, in the words of Claire Colebrook, is “not the ground or foundation of life; the plane of immanence is the thought of that which produces any ground” (2001, p. 77).

With this understanding of philosophy in place, we are able to move beyond the grip of representation and measure philosophy in terms of effectivity. The creation of concepts underwrites the actualization of virtual relations and as a corollary establishes an interconnection between the virtual and the actual, not due to concepts’ ability to refer, but to concepts’ ability to express sense. As we have seen, sense belongs to the virtual realm, but is also always part of the actual world. Reality is never fully grasped unless both virtual intensities and actual states of affairs are accounted for (Spangenberg, 2009).

The Active Life

We now turn to Hannah Arendt. In *The Human Condition*, Arendt discusses three activities that underpin human life: labor, work and action. Each activity corresponds to a basic human condition. The basic condition for labor is life itself. We need to labor to provide ourselves with the necessities of food and shelter. The corresponding condition for work is worldliness. Through work humans create a shared world in the form of communities, objects and culture. Action corresponds to the basic condition of plurality. Action can only take place in the presence of other people. All three activities and their corresponding conditions are underpinned by the conditions for life: natality and mortality. Natality signifies a new beginning—we are born into this world as newcomers, which always implies that new actions are initiated and that the consequences reach beyond our grasp and control. In action and speech, we disclose not just the action in itself but *who* we are. Unlike labor and work, action can never be tamed nor performed in a way in which the individual loses its *who*.

Judgment

Arendt’s notion of judgment is based on Kant’s notion of aesthetic judgment and *sensus communis*, respectively. An aesthetic judgment can be deductive or reflective; the former moves from the general to the particular and the latter moves from the particular to the general. For Kant, judgment is the ability to think the particular as subsumed under a universal. Through the particular we can ascend to the generality of a certain concept; for instance, stumbling upon a beautiful sculpture might give one an understanding of what beauty is. It is only through the particular that the universal can arise. In the particular, we can see the universal at the same time as the particular retains its particularity. For Arendt, it is the spectators that are in a position to judge events impartially. To do this, they make use of two faculties: imagination and common sense. Imagination means that we represent for our mind events that have already taken place; this representation thus establishes a distance from which we can make a disinterested judgment. When this distance has been established, we can view the representations from multiple perspectives;

that is, we are able to enact representative thinking. The other faculty that spectators have to make use of is common sense or *sensus communis*, since without it, spectators would not be able to transcend their subjective position of judging. Hence, judgments need to be communicable intersubjectively with other members of the same community. Arendt again draws on Kant and uses the notion of an “enlarged mentality” in order to show how the spectator’s verdict, although impartial, still relies on the views of others (1981, p. 94). A spectator is thus withdrawn from the scene of action to be able to understand the spectacle.

Two Types of Common Sense

Israeli philosopher Itay Snir points out that “The most radical aspect of Arendt’s conception of common sense” (2020, p. 73) is that it does not exist automatically in a society: it has to be created and maintained continuously. We judge within a common sense, but we also intervene and reconstruct common sense through our judging actions. Common-sense understanding and reasoning is not a static feature of the world; rather, it is brought forward by people inhabiting a specific place in which common sense is always up for grabs. The corresponding worldly property of our sixth sense, common sense, is realness:

In a world of appearances, filled with error and semblance, reality is guaranteed by this three-fold commonness: the five senses, utterly different from each other, have the same object in common, members of the same species have the context in common that endows every single object with its particular meaning; and all other sense-endowed beings, though perceiving this object from utterly different perspectives, agree on its identity. Out of this threefold commonness arises the *sensation* of reality. (Arendt, 1981, p. 50)

Although our sixth sense is not strictly speaking a sense on par with our five senses, since its worldly property cannot be perceived, it brings about a sensation of realness, a thereness, which always takes place in a specific context of appearances (1981, p. 51). We can identify two types of common sense herein: i) common sense as imagination, representation and judgment (an enlarged mentality); ii) common sense as a sixth sense which brings about the sensation of realness, anchored in the functions and worldly properties of our five general senses. Both of these understandings of common sense are targets for Deleuze’s criticism, as we saw above.

Thinking as Afterthought and the Creation of Meaning

Thinking for Arendt is the silent dialogue between me and myself. Thinking demands a withdrawal from everyday practice, from the world of appearances, in that the thinking process, although prompted by everyday experience, needs to de-sense that which has appeared in order for the thinking process to create “thought-things.” Thus, common sense, our sensation of realness, is suspended in the act of thinking (1981, p. 52).

Thinking is always an afterthought; it comes *after the event*. The afterthought can suddenly hit us, creep up on us, as it were, or be voluntarily recalled and mulled over. In the search for meaning, which the afterthought gives rise to, we do not simply replay events that have taken place, but rather pick them apart and move beyond them as part of the search for meaning. That is, in thinking

we recall events *and* create meaning for further thought; thought always goes further (Arendt, 1981). Thus, within the thinking process that Arendt discusses, we can see similarities with Deleuze's actual-virtual dimensions of thinking and reality, in that thinking and the creation of meaning are never conditioned by a foreseeable terminus.

When we think, we are in solitude, and we present for our minds episodes that have already taken place. In this re-presentation we rely on both memory and imagination. Note that although the contingency of everyday appearances is of a different order than the thinking process itself, the former gives rise to the latter. The activity of thinking has no goal that lies outside of itself; rather, the process of thinking in itself is the aim. Moreover, when the thinking process comes to an end, we find ourselves back in the everyday world of appearances in which doing, and not thinking, takes place. When we are in the midst of everyday practice, for instance when we are engaged in a lively discussion with friends, we are not thinking, although we obviously make use of our cognitive abilities, since we are not in solitude, which is the prerequisite of having an inner dialogue between me and myself.

Thinking, Knowledge and Judging

Arendt differentiates thinking from knowing. Knowing is concerned with truth, whereas thinking is concerned with meaning. Thinking concerns itself with unanswerable questions, and there is no finality to the process of thinking in the form of a tangible object, which is the success of knowledge. Through thinking, we seek to understand the meaning of events in which the taxonomy of true and false has no abode. However, this does not mean that meaning and truth are fully separate. Thinking arises from knowledge, and knowledge would be impossible to obtain without thinking. Yet while related, they are of different orders, as we have seen.

For Arendt, the faculty of judging is interrelated with the faculty of thinking in that thinking has a liberating effect on the judging spectator who realizes thinking in the public realm, in which thinking itself can never take place. Judging thus makes thinking manifest, a "thinking" that is not knowledge but the ability to tell right from wrong, beautiful from ugly. The difference between thinking and judging is that judging takes place in the world of appearances, whereas thinking demands a withdrawal from that very same world. However, judging is the ability both to tell right from wrong and to draw on our imagination in order to enact representative thinking. Thus, we are thinking, but in the form of a spectator in whom the inner dialogue between me and myself is not actualized. The withdrawal demanded by the spectator is one from action rather than one from the world of appearances. The withdrawal is necessary in order to see the whole. But it does not demand solitude. On the contrary, the spectator's verdict depends on the views of others, an "enlarged mentality," as Arendt explained in her lectures on Kant. Judging, like thinking, takes place in isolation, in the moment when imagination is used to represent the perspective of other people. The withdrawal of judgment, unlike thinking, is still located within the world of appearances. However, the precondition for representative thinking is interaction with other people in a shared world in which common sense is created.

Thinking, as we have seen, does not yield tangible rules of conduct or a stable foundation for acting morally. What it does yield is a critical examination of present norms, conventions and political systems that are contingent and thus always open for discussion and change. Conscience is a

byproduct of thinking that stems from the inner dialogue between me and myself. The ground for telling right from wrong is “subjective in two senses. First, what I can bear to have done without losing my internal harmony might change from one individual to another, or depend on historical and political circumstances. Second, moral judgments turn on the question of with whom I wish to be, namely on something resembling concrete human interaction, not on abstract standards and rules that allow for Platonic objectivity” (Snir, 2020, p. 64). Although thinking deals with invisibles while judgment deals with particulars, they are interconnected, as we have seen, in that thinking is actualized in judgment, when we tell right from wrong, but without instating universal rules of conduct.

Thus, thinking dissolves firm categories and prepares the activity of judging particulars without using universals as guideposts. In other words, judgment is our public manifestation of thinking critically. Thinking thus gives options for actions. So judgment is our outer manifestation of thought; but how do we communicate our thinking to other people? Arendt, again following Kant, proposes metaphors as mediators for thinking. Through metaphorical language, we can make manifest the *experience of thinking* and not the thinking process itself, since it demands solitude. The experience of thinking is transferred in speech through metaphorical language. In Arendt’s words,

Analogies, metaphors, and emblems are the threads by which the mind holds on to the world even when, absentmindedly, it has lost direct contact with it, and they guarantee the unity of human experience. Moreover, in the thinking process itself they serve as models to give us our bearings lest we stagger blindly among experiences that our bodily senses with their relative certainty of knowledge cannot guide us through. The simple fact that our mind is able to find such analogies, that the world of appearances reminds us of things non-apparent, may be seen as a kind of “proof” that mind and body, thinking and sense experience, the invisible and the visible, belong together, are “made” for each other, as it were. (1981, p. 109)

Metaphors bring together the invisible and the visible. The abyss between the two modes is thus bridged. The ongoing process of thinking, Arendt says, is like “Penelope’s web; it undoes every morning what it has finished the night before” (1981, p. 88). But the “only possible” metaphor for thinking itself, Arendt states, “is the sensation of being alive” (1981, p. 123). A potential danger with all thinking, Arendt claims, is to confuse thinking with a withdrawal from the world of human affairs. We have seen that thinking indeed demands solitude; however, solitude is not to be confused with loneliness. Thinking is, furthermore, always tied to action, and action always takes place amid fellow individuals. This is why Arendt draws on Socrates in fleshing out the life of the mind, in that he operated in the *polis* and tried to draw out truth from opinions (*doxa*). That is, he did not try to impose philosophical truths upon opinions, but rather engaged in dialogue, trying to make *doxa* more truthful.

So, thinking is both something that takes place in solitude, in the inner dialogue between me and myself, and an outer manifestation in judgment and action. In action, we are in the world of appearances, and when acting, we are judged by spectators who make use of imagination and common sense to evaluate the actions on display. Both action and judgment are underpinned by plurality.

Arendt and Deleuze Making (Common) Sense

Imagination is used by both Arendt and Deleuze to transcend our own narrow subject and our human point of view as a way of unleashing thinking from firm banisters. The philosophy of common sense that Deleuze criticizes is one in which sense is defined as the condition of truth, whereas Arendt defines common sense as a political faculty in which opinions are formed. Within the philosophy of Arendt, thinking, judgment and action are ontologically rooted in natality and plurality. The initiation of something new, conditioned by the fact that we are born into a world populated by other acting subjects, shapes our course of action from the viewpoint of the actor, and our ability to judge from the standpoint of the spectator. We are free to act and judge in the sense that we are unique and able to set something in motion. However, this freedom is hinged on the unexpectedness of action and does not stem from an isolated will. The subject never acts alone; its uniqueness and ability to act and judge is dependent on other people, that is, on plurality. Through the faculty of imagination, we are able to represent other people's viewpoints from the standpoint of our subjective selves. This imagination is preconditioned by the actual involvement and interaction with other people. Thus, Arendt is not assuming an established image of thought before representative thinking is enacted.

The notion of common sense that Deleuze is attacking is one in which all our faculties are understood to work together to recognize, identify and subsume. This is how common sense is reproduced; we merely recognize, and in recognizing, we are not thinking, since we are under the chairmanship of the dogmatic image of thought. Thinking, for Deleuze, is preceded by a shocking encounter with an object that forces us to think and on which our senses no longer work jointly to recognize; from the view of perception, what we encounter is imperceptible.

Arendt, like Deleuze, draws on Kant's understanding of common sense, which, as we have seen, moves beyond the mere harmonizing exercise of our five senses. Whilst Deleuze settles with the understanding of common sense as recognition and doxa, Arendt pushes the envelope further in positing a common sense that is always in flux, and not a natural part of a society; it is always being created, maintained, eradicated. Moreover, common sense for Arendt is pre-conditioned by the interaction with others, but not in a fashion that leads to expressions, such as "everybody knows what it means to think." On the contrary, Arendt's *sensus communis* thrives on plurality and difference, on the cultivation of different perspectives and standpoints. Thinking, strictly speaking, is not taking place in common sense for Arendt, just as for Deleuze. However, thinking, for Arendt, must always return to doxa to make sense, and to being part and parcel of our world of appearances. Through this move, Arendt inserts an element of thinking also within doxa—not the pure activity which demands solitude, but one instantiated in the spectator and the actor. From within common sense, thinking and action can thus emerge for Arendt, which for Deleuze suggests something close to an abomination in that the very "thinking" would be circumscribed by the dogmatic image of thought *which thinking contends to transcend*. However, that Deleuzian understanding becomes circumscribed itself, I claim, when plurality and difference are purged from the notion at the outset. His particular understanding of commonsensical reasoning as solely transmitted through recognition is a definition of common sense that Arendt seeks to transcend, but without throwing the baby out with the bathwater. When Arendt and Socrates roam the streets of the polis, they discover that *not* everybody knows what it means to think, and that it is *not* a natural capacity. A possible reply to my claim that Deleuze's conception of common sense

becomes circumscribed itself would be that common sense, in that it is representational and moral, is by necessity disconnected from virtual intensities and becomings. In line with this objection is the objection that Arendt's understanding of common sense, and of thinking and judging, is hinged on a presupposed subject that initiates independent action in this world. I believe that this tension is more apparent than real in that Deleuze's point of departure is the immanent difference of virtual events that are interconnected with actual states of affairs, whereas Arendt's point of departure is the acting and thinking subject contained within actual states of affairs. These two presuppositions are seemingly at odds with one another, but only if we close ourselves off to the virtual relationship between them. For instance, Deleuze claims that to stay close to the event, we have to enact counter-actualizations in the actual world. Arendt's judging spectator who says "no" to business as usual is, I claim, an example of a counter-actualization. Furthermore, Deleuze's notion of virtual intensities expands Arendt's notion of common sense and shows how we could transcend doxa with our faculty of thinking that, as a consequence, moves beyond a traditional or stale understanding of representational thinking. Thus, the Arendtian standpoint of another person need not solely be perceived as different *from* mine; it is different *in itself*.

With Arendt's notions of common sense and judgment, Deleuze's understanding of the interconnection between virtual intensities and actual states of affairs can be expanded upon through understanding Arendt's subject as anchored in a common world yet endowed with a faculty of thinking (and judgment) that never comes to a halt or relies upon logical principles.

Implications for Education

Education, for both Arendt and Deleuze, needs to move beyond the mere transmission of knowledge. In *Proust and Signs* (2000), Deleuze spells out an apprenticeship that the protagonist of Proust's *In Search of Lost Time* is undergoing. *The search*, for Deleuze, is not oriented towards the past but towards the future. Along the way, the protagonist learns that objects emitting signs do not contain the secret of the sign, and neither does the subjective interpreter. However, it is through the engagement with other people that the protagonist of the search comes to understand the process of explicating signs and rids himself of the illusions of pure objectivity and pure subjective interpretive associations. He comes to learn that essences, or what Deleuze deems differences, are internal in both objects and subjects alike, and that the signs being emitted need to be explicated rather than represented; we need to unfold that which the sign enfolds. We can read this approach through Arendt's understanding of the representation of other people's viewpoints from the viewpoint of oneself: *I think from where I stand, imagining that it could be different—the world as much as my outlook*.

Arendt's plurality and unicity bring about unexpected encounters, events, that give rise to thought that goes further than the identification of the emitted sign, that is the person/situation we come across, and looks for meaning and difference that demand explication rather than simple representation. However, a precondition for learning, or apprenticeship, for Arendt is to get to know the old world. Children must be taught our collective accumulated body of knowledge, customs and common sense to properly immerse themselves therein *and* to subsequently change it. In this regard, education must be conservative. Important to note is that the task of familiarizing youngsters with the old world for Arendt is not equivalent to inculcation, but, rather, to assuming responsibility for a future to come. Thus, the responsibility to acquaint the youngsters with the

old world stipulates more than the mere transmission of knowledge.

Deleuze would claim that however necessary, this is not education for thinking, but only for recognition. However, without the first step of recognition, we would be completely unmoored from the world and unable to cultivate thinking and open ourselves up to rare encounters and events. Of course, what Deleuze cautions against is the danger and inertia of *remaining* within the confines of common sense (and confusing structure of thought for thinking), not our colloquial usage of it. What we can learn from Arendt is that representation and explication must not be oppositional. When we represent, imagining a different viewpoint, we are in a position to judge things differently, counter to common sense, which in itself bears the power of changing common sense. Our judging faculty bears the promise of creation, and creation is always an event. For Arendt, common sense contains not only uncontested mundane knowledge from which we derive temporary “truths” and permissible conduct, but a sensation of realness that functions as an arena for action. When we act, we act as a response to the actions of others, and these others can readily be expanded to encompass signs, mental and physical objects, technology, natural phenomena and so forth, and remain consistent with Arendt’s philosophy at large.

Within a Deleuzian creative process, there is an Idea that is constitutive of problems. Common sense is for Arendt created rather than discovered. In representative thinking, we tackle head-on the problem of natality, the new beginning inherent in all actions unfolding from a specific point of view. Always different, always fleeting. Thinking in terms of creating concepts, in terms of withdrawal from the world of appearances and in terms of representative thinking, are all on par with being “worthy of the event,” in that sense resides in the problem itself. It is not about finding proper solutions to well-defined problems, but to continue thinking and expressing that sense/event through action and speech.

In education, then, Arendt’s and Deleuze’s common sense can join forces and point towards the cultivation of thinking: firstly, through getting to know the old world, and secondly, by creating a new one. Snir (2020) proposes that the inner dialogue between me and myself, a withdrawal from the world of appearances, is complemented with the faculty of judgment that thinking in solitude liberates. In an educational context, this can be formed as giving space for students to contemplate and engage with their peers through dialogue that opens up the possibility for actualizing representative thinking. A common sense is then both established and challenged in concert, with no pre-given goal as to where to arrive.

So, what can we learn from Arendt and Deleuze? From Arendt, we learn about a continuous inner dialogue from which public judgment can be cultivated. From Deleuze, we learn about the explicating process of interpreting signs from which sense and pure difference can be derived, paired with the creation of concepts.

A cultivation of judgment from thinking, and an open-ended examining of pre-suppositions (very much similar to getting to know the old world), can be merged, I claim, in that both steer us to move beyond business as usual, not for the sake of moving beyond—it is not the end-goal—but for the sake of creating a better world in which movement of thought can be actualized. Thus, for both Arendt and Deleuze, the main question is not what we can know *but what we can become*.

Conclusion

In this paper, I inquired into the concepts of common sense, thinking and the event through engaging with the philosophies of Hannah Arendt and Gilles Deleuze. I showed that common sense can be understood as both an intersubjective faculty in which opinions are formed and a representative thought-scheme that imprisons thought through actualizing recognition and identification rather than creative thinking. However, these two aspects are both important to keep in mind while examining the origin of common sense *and* thinking. When we realize that common sense imposes a thought-regime in which recognition is taken as an in-principle transcendental faculty of human perception, then we can more easily catch a sight of creative thought, thinking, as a process that momentarily captures pure difference.

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Love and Education Beyond the Event Horizon: An Apology to Christopher Nolan

Andrew Gibbons

Introduction

This paper engages with the concept of love in education through an analysis of the motion picture *Interstellar* by Christopher Nolan. Love is taken as a necessarily tricky, elusive, concept—taking for granted that anything that appears simple and predictable might be some kind of love-like thing, but not the kind of love that is of interest here. The love of interest here is a kind of gravity-shattering force that releases the sciences from their epistemological event horizons. It's love, but not as 'we' know it (the 'we' here referring to any culture that has typically disregarded or marginalised love in some way).

Interstellar adds some complexity to working philosophically with love in education through its association of love with event horizons—the film takes up something of a logic and a science of love to suggest that love is both an essential condition and a provocation for thinking through the seemingly impossible equations that confound the physical sciences. Those associations are explored through the flows of the narrative, and observations of a selection of key characters.

The application of Nolan's work on love is speculative, presenting a sense of the ways in which science fiction might offer the philosophy of education different tools to tinker with the things that matter. "Science fiction, in our reading of it, does not need to stand up to science in order to be effective ... it gives us license to engage in a series of aesthetic thought experiments, of what currently is and where it might go" (Gibbons and Kupferman, 2019, pp. 168-169). In this paper, that tinkering is explored as resonant with the work of Heidegger and Camus. Both writers are read here as offering a way into science fiction as poetic work in the philosophy of education. Their respective questions with regard science lend a hand to the task of questioning science and education through science fiction.

In the study of education, science fiction is educational in its engagement with speculation on the what ifs and the why nots: speculations that are not simply future focused, but rather are approaches to imagining the already present. For example, first contact with a galaxy travelling civilisation is not limited to thinking ahead, it is also productive for thinking back (the abiding narratives that generate thoughts about colonisation) and the present (the ways in which a society or community might not notice that which is already at hand). Science fiction

demands something of the imagination, in a way that sparks a wonder. Here wonder is more than simply a curiosity about the future; wonder generates both present and future in its existentially generative sense..... [W]ithin this concept of wonder, kept at arm's length from the cold calculations and measurements of an analytic mind, is a more radical imagination of new questions, and an intensification of these questions

concerning being in the present. (Gibbons and Kupferman, 2019, p 170)

Using science fiction to explore love and education adds to existing scholarly engagement on, for just a few examples, love and pedagogy (Goldstein, 1997; Page, 2018), love and the purpose of education (Lin, 2006), love and child rearing (de Grice, Braun, and Wetherell, 2017), love and community (Cram, 2021) and love and critical education (Lanas and Zembylas, 2015).

When using cinema, science fiction or otherwise, to engage with the philosophy of education, it's perhaps important to first make disclaimers and alerts. A disclaimer: this is not a cinematic review of the film within the field of cinematic studies. While the work here may add to cinematic studies, that is not its purpose. An alert: If the reader has not seen *Interstellar* then this article is full of spoilers. I recommend putting the paper down and watching the film. However, I also recognise that reading about a film and watching that same film can happen in any order with generative implications, particularly if being conditioned and warned as to (an interpretation of) the film's devices is not a problem.

In this paper, the thinking that is nurtured through an exploration of *Interstellar* is then applied to education policy and curriculum through two contexts: 1) epistemological debates concerning scientific and “Indigenous knowledge” (Stewart, 2021a, p. 2) systems in one bicultural nation; and 2) early childhood care and education as a distinct and problematic education ‘sector’ in many nations. Early childhood education and care is of interest here because of its nearness to the problem of love in education and because of the direct reference to love through the concept of *aroha* in *Mātauranga Māori*—a reference that symbolises a persistent tension for curriculum and policy writers, and for the children and adults who come together to form early childhood care and education communities.

Interstellar

The central characters in *Interstellar* are Coop and Murph—father and daughter. Other characters of interest include the black hole Gargantua, the robot TARS and the astronaut scientists Mann and Brand.

When we meet the Coopers, Murph is talking about a ghost in her room. She's not scared of the ghost; rather, she thinks it's trying to communicate with her. Coop argues that suggesting there's a ghost trying to communicate with her is not very scientific. Murph replies to Coop, “you said science is about admitting what we don't know.” Coop then encourages Murph to start observing the phenomenon, gathering all the facts. Coop is especially proud of Murph and her love of science, so inviting her to gather all the facts is not undermining or dismissing a daughter, but rather a celebration of knowing a daughter—he loves Murph, and knows what makes Murph tick.

This love for Murph plays out in a scene at school. Coop is brought in to talk to the principal and to Murph's teacher about Murph's behaviour. Murph has been fighting, which is concerning. But more concerning for the teacher is that Murph is fighting about a disagreement over a book of Coop's that she brought to school. The book speaks of a history in which an organisation called NASA chose to go to the moon. As such, this book is banned at school for spreading misinformation about the space race of the mid-twentieth century. The moon landing never

happened. Murph's teacher explains with certainty that the moon landing was a conspiracy.

In *Interstellar*, a teacher can genuinely, and with an unquestioning faith, state the moon landing was a cunning fiction designed to undermine the Soviet Union during the Cold War—convincing the Soviet Union to invest in a mythical space race gives the United States some breathing space. Those that talked of conspiracies to manufacture the moon landing were right—it was a conspiracy. Anyone who now suggests that NASA did actually land on the moon is the new conspiracy theorist undermining humanity's mission to save a dying planet. Conveniently then, it is organisations like NASA that can be shown to be responsible for the predicament of the planet (Peters et al., 2021). In *Interstellar*, a good teacher and a good curriculum is concerned with a rationality that allows for the greatest number to survive without further environmental degradation. But the clock is ticking, and no one seems to seriously think there's any possibility of saving the planet.

Coop is unwilling to believe that there is no future. He is ex-NASA and believes that living the best life involves looking up to the stars and believing in an extra-terrestrial future for humanity. So, Coop is also unwilling to discipline Murph for her behaviour at school. The teacher and principal are mocked by Coop, who advises them he is going to punish Murph by treating her to a baseball game.

Murph, meanwhile, is happily gathering data on a phenomenon with a thorough and rational belief that something is trying to communicate with her, and that her father and brother are playfully dismissing it as a ghost. Coop's failure to believe in an entity trying to communicate with Murph is ironic, because it's actually him attempting to communicate with himself through Murph. And paradoxically, if he is successful in the future at stopping himself in the past, he never ends up in that future, at least as far as we can make sense of time at the moment. Present Coop is failing to listen to future Coop in warning present Coop to stay on Earth and not fly through a mysterious wormhole leading to a new and potentially habitable galaxy of planets.

When Coop realises that there is indeed something communicating with Murph, and that it is communicating in binary, he discovers the coordinates to a secret NASA base where NASA is working on an equation that will enable an exodus from the dying Earth. Solving the problem of gravity appears unlikely, so, at the same time, NASA is sending human embryos through a wormhole that has been deposited near Saturn and appears to be a benign intervention aimed at opening access to habitable planets in another galaxy.

Having not heeded his own future warning to himself, Coop travels through the wormhole and ends up in a system of three potentially habitable planets orbiting a black hole that NASA has decided to call Gargantua. Gargantua is explained as a collapsed star. Nothing escapes Gargantua's event horizon, not even light, although this debated astrophysical theory (see Curiel, 2019) regarding the inescapability of events beyond the event horizon turns out to be incorrect. All the same, NASA plans to send in a probe to gather data, believing that somewhere beyond this inescapable event horizon is an answer, and that maybe for a brief moment some data can be relayed out of the black hole by the probe.

Gargantua has a huge gravitational pull, and the closer that the expedition flies to it, the more their

experience of time slows down compared to Earth. The team has to decide just how much time they can lose and return to an Earth still habited by their loved ones. In arguing over which habitable planet to head to in this new galaxy, Brand, who happens to be in love with one of the three astronauts alone on one of the three potentially habitable planets, argues that following one's heart could be a legitimate approach to solving the problem of which direction to take. Brand argues that "we've spent too long trying to figure [time and gravity] out with theory." She goes on: "Love isn't something we invented, it's observable, powerful. It has to have meaning." Love, Brand argues, "is the one thing that we're capable of perceiving that transcends time and space." Love might bust through the apparently impervious event horizon, and so events become newly available from beyond the horizon.

Gargantua is a key character in *Interstellar*, offering an event horizon past, or perhaps through, which humanity hopes it might find paradigm-changing formulae—answers to questions that have yet to be asked. For the science of *Interstellar*, Gargantua offers challenges to experiences of time and gravity, and their association with yet to be discovered dimensions (Davis, 2021). Nolan worked with astrophysicists in creating Gargantua, in order to "attempt depicting a black hole as it would actually be seen by somebody nearby" (James et al., 2015, p. 1). The aim was to "make the film as scientifically accurate as possible—within constraints of not confusing his mass audience unduly and using images that are exciting and fresh" (James et al., 2015, p. 22). Gargantua, then, in a sense, invites us to wonder whether there's something beyond the horizons of science within the black hole—and who is to say that whatever that something unimaginable is, that it might not be love? Coop, driven by a concern to return to earth with a minimal loss of years, disregards Brand's appeal to a new theory of love, and they head off to Dr. Mann's planet.

The leader of a previous expedition through the wormhole, Dr. Mann is considered a hero because he committed to a mission which had little chance of success and most likely would result in him dying alone on an uninhabitable planet. It was a one-way trip unless the planet was habitable. Dr. Mann has a change of heart. He decides he does not want to sacrifice his life for humanity when he realises the planet is uninhabitable, and he tricks Coop and the rest of the team in order to escape the planet and save himself. Mann apologises to Coop as he smashes Coop's space suit and leaves Coop to die on the planet. Mann's apology takes the form of an ironic lecture on how the imagination of loved ones will be the last thing Coop thinks of. Mann explains that this connection to loved ones is humanity's greatest source of inspiration—the human survival instinct is powered by intimacy. That intimacy, Dr. Mann argues, "rarely extends beyond our line of sight." Mann theorises love as an evolutionary function. He ascribes a scientific rationale for love in this sense; however, it's limited to survival in the face of adversity. Love conjures up loved ones to generate a little more desire to stay alive.

Coop manages to survive Dr. Mann's attack on his spacesuit, chases after Dr. Mann, and Dr. Mann then dies attempting to steal Coop's ship in a bid to return to a dying Earth.

Then, and this is important, Coop sacrifices himself for the mission, propelling Brand to the final possible habitable planet, exhausting his own fuel and getting sucked into Gargantua. This is where we find out that

- a) There is indeed dimension-changing data to see once inside the black hole, beyond the event horizon
- b) You can escape a black hole

In *Gargantua*, Coop finds himself in a visual and physical representation of Murph's room back on Earth, a representation which he can alter. It's now that Coop realises it was him sending messages to Murph, including the coordinates for NASA and the warning to stay on Earth. He also realises that Brand was right—that there is a quantifiable love between father and daughter that enables a power of connection that transcends time and space. Coop realises that this representation of Murph's room, and the wormhole itself, are not gifts from a benign intergalactic Santa Claus, but rather an access key and blueprint from his own human future. With the help of the robot TARS, Coop uses this connection to transmit the secrets of *Gargantua* as data to Murph, data which enables Murph to complete the necessary equations for escaping the gravity of Earth.

Coop achieves the seemingly impossible. He crosses a conceptual threshold and discovers a new truth to the appearance of the event horizon. *Gargantua* sucks him beyond the horizon. The love that matters here is the love that confounds Dr. Mann. Coop submits himself to the gravity of *Gargantua* and gets pulled into the black hole, accepting that he will not escape, he will not see Murph again. There are some complex love equations to explore here. Love reveals a connection that transcends time and space, and love reveals a capacity to throw oneself into an apparent void.

The apology: Love, science and philosophy

This paper is developed as an apology because I was initially critical and dismissive of the positioning of love as a *deus ex machina* described above. Perhaps not as much as TV science and technology personality Adam Savage (2014), who shared in a review of the film, "I was not moved by the plot, even a little bit ... the plot of *Interstellar* left me cold cold cold and I was very sad about that." One might argue that being left feeling cold is a kind of movement that is worth exploring. I too felt a little cold, hostile to the use of love to solve the necessary equations and resolve the problem of escaping a poorly (if at all) loved Earth. This device seemed to be cheap.

Over time, this analysis appeared more than just unnecessarily hostile; it failed to see nuance in Brand's hypothesis and in Coop's experiment. Here I want to challenge that it is important to explore what Brand might offer when she argues that "we've spent too long trying to figure [time and gravity] out with theory," to recognise persistent challenges to what counts as science, and to speculate on some alternative ways of thinking through the themes of love and science in the philosophy of education.

Brand needn't think of love as some kind of theory vacuum. Recognising that love "isn't something we invented, it's observable, powerful" is entirely theoretical. What Brand might be taken to mean to say is that there's been a tendency to look behind only some select bushes (Nietzsche, 1979) for the right scientific theories. Brand challenges that it is time to look behind bushes that have been disregarded for their relevance to seemingly proper questions concerning science.

Brand is asking that her colleagues reconceptualise what is and what is not scientific. This is a

debate of significance in Aotearoa New Zealand, with particular concern for the ways in which claims to what counts as scientific legitimacy has led to a recognition of the ways in which epistemological chauvinisms (Young, 2002) continue to operate in a supposedly bicultural nation that is bonded in partnership by a treaty which acknowledges the knowledge rights of the treaty partners.

As the nation explores more deeply and broadly what such a partnership might mean for bicultural epistemologies, a hostility has amplified with regard to cultural knowledge, with claims from within the academic science community that cultural knowledge is of cultural importance for cultures, but cannot make claims to being scientific knowledge (see Stewart, 2021a). In this debate, the public of Aotearoa New Zealand has been served a “warning that science is being attacked by Mātauranga Māori” (Stewart, 2021a, p. 1). In exploring the political and philosophical dimensions of this debate, Stewart explains, “traditional Māori cosmogenic and nature narratives taken together make up the paradigm and philosophy of mātauranga, within which Māori empirical knowledge is organised and makes sense” (Stewart, 2022, p. 22).

Stewart counters concerns with regard to any apparent undermining of science with the challenge that “the boundary between science and Indigenous knowledge has historically helped science to define itself” (Stewart, 2021a, p. 2), hence challenging the grounds upon which any warning to the public might be made. At the same time, Stewart (2022) offers a challenge to any attempts to see science and Mātauranga Māori as commensurate with particular attention to the observation that there’s little agreement on what counts as science (Stewart, 2022). Stewart (2022, p. 19) argues:

All cultural knowledges or ethnosciences involve knowledge of nature, collect evidence using the human senses, and use logical thinking to process experience and guide decision-making. In this sense, mātauranga counts as a science. But such general descriptors do not justify the claim that all cultural knowledge bases are therefore “the same” as contemporary science knowledge. (Stewart, 2022, p. 20)

Brand’s problem is then one which might open her up to the colonising tendencies of a science that she has long been dedicated to, but for which she had lacked the philosophical imagination to see beyond.

A key challenge for Brand is to avoid any theory of the transcendence of love being assimilated into a narrowed understanding of what counts as science. This is an essential concern with a significant history and contemporary relevance for knowledge. Stewart (2022, p. 21) suggests that

To examine the relationship between mātauranga and science shines a light on the “invisible” philosophy of science. In this sense, mātauranga acts as a mirror for science: a way for Western knowledge to see beyond its blinkers, to gain more understanding of itself and its own limitations.

Seeing beyond these blinkers might draw on the horizon-imagining experimentations of philosophical work. Here I would like to consider briefly the work of just two philosophers: Heidegger and Camus. These two are of particular relevance to an analysis of *Interstellar* because their questions concerning science come from an attention to an aesthetic that invites closer

attention to the poetic and, possibly, to love.

Camus, in *The Myth of Sisyphus*, speaks directly to science and a love for the world. He recognises that through science he might learn to settle upon certain truths of the quantum nature of things, but that the

science that was ready to teach me everything ends up in a hypothesis, that lucidity founders in metaphor, that uncertainty is resolved in a work of art. What need had I of so many efforts? The soft lines of these hills and the hand of evening on this troubled heart reach me much more. I have returned to my beginning. I realize that if through science I can seize phenomena and enumerate them, I cannot, for all that, apprehend the world. Were I to trace its entire relief with my finger, I should not know any more. (Camus, 1991, p. 20)

Camus offers this approach to an epistemological release through an attention to the beauty that is on the horizon. His troubled heart is massaged by his love for the world. His love for the world offers a sense of the horizons of a science that lacks a philosophical reflexivity (Stewart, 2022). Camus offers this sense through the release of poetry. Heidegger's concern for dwelling and measuring offers a similar release.

Through the poetry of Hölderlin, Heidegger (1971) wonders on poetry establishing a grounding, an earthing, that brings about dwelling. In *Building Dwelling Thinking*, Heidegger (1993a) continues on a path of questioning technology and human being. He questions what it means to, in particular, build and dwell, offering that “dwelling itself is always a staying with things” (Heidegger, 1993a, p. 353) and that learning to dwell is being in the world. Dwelling invokes a relationship of caring for, and of giving presence to (Heidegger, 1993a).

Heidegger's observation of the problem with thinking about measurement makes sense when considering Brand's problem. Heidegger (1971, p. 224) says:

When we hear of measure, we immediately think of number and imagine the two, measure and number, as quantitative. But the *nature* of measure is no more a quantum than is the *nature* of a number. True, we can reckon with numbers—but not with the nature of number. When Hölderlin envisages poetry as a measuring, and above all himself achieves poetry as taking measure ... we must pay heed to the kind of taking here, which does not consist in a clutching or any other kind of grasping, but rather in a letting come of what has been dealt out.

Through a questioning of measuring, Heidegger offers a recognition of the limits of science and of theorising that concerns Brand and that leads her to wonder about what might be offered in thinking about love. Love and poetry need not be seen as interchangeable here. Rather, love like poetry invites a different way of thinking through being and measuring that offers a way into thinking about dimensionality:

The upward glance passes aloft toward the sky, and yet it remains below on the earth. The upward glance spans the between of sky and earth. This between is measured out

for the dwelling of man. We now call the span thus meted out the dimension. This dimension does not arise from the fact that sky and earth are turned toward one another. Rather, their facing each other itself depends on the dimension. Nor is the dimension a stretch of space as ordinarily understood; for everything spatial, as something for which space is made, is already in need of the dimension, that is, that into which it is admitted. (Heidegger, 1971, p. 220)

A turn to love is here understood as a philosophical and educational turn, an opening up to love as educational in the sense of a deep connection to the world. As poetry might be seen to cause dwelling (Heidegger, 1971), perhaps then love can be seen to cause learning.

To play with this idea further, should children be studying love instead of studying calculus and physics at school? And might they discover the events beyond event horizons staying right here on Earth? Would a curriculum focused on love unlock the mysteries of time and gravity? Maybe, maybe not. What I'd like to propose is that this new curriculum would offer many other mysteries to explore, mysteries concerning care of the planet and everything on it, and caring for the horizons that disclose being.

Of course, one should be careful with sharing such innovations with policy makers in a Modern educational system. Suggesting that love should be a part of the curriculum could translate into an instrumental social conditioning, producing a series of normalised and enframing beliefs, ideas and practice, a measuring of the truths of love, and assessment of whether children meet the love grade. In other words, when Brand observes that maybe science needs to take more notice of love, whatever might be worth noticing could slip through anxiously clutching hands.

Camus' exploration of atoms and the horizon in *The Myth of Sisyphus* and Heidegger's work with dimensionality in "...*Poetically Man Dwells...*" might provide alternative readings on love and science for this curriculum. Heidegger's thinking might stretch dimensionality beyond the ordinary notions of measurement and bring new dimension to dimensions through a poetry of dwelling and measuring, an attention to the "breadth of being" (1971, p. 222). Curriculum-wise, this turn might look like a slowing down of the measuring events that happen in education systems to, in Heidegger's words, "pay heed" (p. 224) to measuring, a "concentrated perception, a gathered taking-in, that remains a listening" (p. 223).

However, in Aotearoa New Zealand, attention to Mātauranga Māori has already been recognised as a way to remove the 'blinkers' of science (Stewart, 2022) or perhaps even move beyond the horizon—that event horizon that Mann chauvinistically regards as rarely crossed. In working with the poetic measuring of dimensions, the nation already has many opportunities. For three very brief examples:

1. Rau and Ritchie (2011) engage the meaning of *whakapapa* as presencing intimate relationships with the Earth and with family, and revealing a different understanding of the temporality of these relationships.
2. Rameka speaks to "Māori perspectives of time ... the past, the present and the future are viewed as intertwined" (Rameka, 2016, p. 387). Life is "a continuous cosmic process"

(Rameka, 2016, p. 387); time is untethered, free from any sense of linearity or even perhaps inevitability. To think of the future as being behind requires thinking about one's position in relation to what is knowable and what can be seen. The experience of time is understood as having spiritual dimensions. Experiences of time are threads that intertwine with experiences of spirituality, family and community, genealogy and so on (Rameka, 2016).

3. Stewart's (2021b, p. 109) recognition of the concept of love in relation to the concept in *te reo Māori* (the Māori language) of *aroha* works with the recognition of love as "infinite." While stressing that the concepts of love and *aroha* are close, they don't "completely match" (Stewart, 2021b, p. 82), and the ways in which their horizons are distinct offers generative educational questions concerning the association of *aroha* with open-mindedness, generosity, and attentiveness, an infinite, "boundless sense of responsibility for the Other" (Stewart, 2021b, p. 83). *Aroha* then puts forth a challenge to Mann with regard just where that line of sight might really end.

While it would be dangerous to suggest Camus, or Heidegger, or *Interstellar's* cosmic flows between daughter and father are in any way analogous with a cosmic perspective of love and life, and the implications of this perspective for a science of event horizons, there is at the same time a resonance that invites wonder. Wondering about time in this way does have its traditional epistemological chauvinisms (Young, 2002) to detether. Allowing for the possibility that love transcends time is however not a new small step for 'man' nor a new giant leap for 'mankind' as humanity looks to reach the stars. Those steps and leaps are ancient to communities that have understood the essence of a relationship to the stars and horizons and events and time and dimensionality and love. The challenge of letting go of predominant understandings of the way in which time works is a challenge of letting go of many apparent Modern comforts and securities. To give up on time would be like giving up on the Internet—it's possibly inconceivable (or at least, the inability to believe in the possibility of an altogether different understanding of time is a very serious condition that defines a process of industrial normalisation and a colonising project that has tick-tocked around the world). If a certain technologically oriented forgetfulness is indeed a condition of Modernity (Heidegger, 1993b), forgetting alternative relationships to time might be one of the key devices for locking thinking into a predictable and inevitable flow that at the same time is the blinkering that denies an open perspective of the cosmos.

Conclusion: Working beyond the event horizon through love and early childhood care and education

This paper concludes with a turn to the context of early childhood care and education and horizons of love. Love and early childhood education sit in a particular relationship that might still make sense and that might offer the philosophy of education a space less hostile to an embracing of love and science. However, this conclusion also shows those philosophical dimensions and possibilities to be under new forms of educational policing through a renewal of very Modern educational traditions in behaviour management—traditions that might be evidence of an absence of love (Lanas and Zembylas, 2015), and that warrant questioning through a theory of love.

In early childhood care and education, an interest in the behavioural sciences fuels a tendency to

work with behaviour management as if it is pedagogy (Arndt, Gibbons, and Fitzsimons, 2015). How does this appear to us? Think of an educational space where all the available spaces on the walls are covered with star charts, loudly proclaiming which children are measuring up to the approved measures of good learning and good behaviour.

The education and care of the child before they reach school age, in many nations around the world, has become a central concern for government. This concern reflects a largely economy-driven realisation in the potential economic benefits of investment in, and regulation of, the child's early care and education experiences. Perhaps most notably, an elevated interest in the care and education of the child is evident in the OECD's comprehensive review of early childhood care and education research and policy—the 'Starting Strong' series (see for instance Barata, 2018). Before starting strong, however, there was an intensification of economic interest and economic thinking in the analysis of longitudinal data of the effects of early childhood care and education for some communities (see for instance Belfield, Nores, Barnett, and Schweinhart, 2006).

This highly technical and pseudo-scientific dimension of educational space might pay heed to measuring through an exploration of love. This exploration is not limited to an affective political operation (Lanas and Zembylas, 2015), but rather opens up to new modes of thinking power and an understanding of thinking as in some kind of interdimensional relationship with emotion, choice, politics and praxis (Lanas and Zembylas, 2015)—a gravity-shattering force and an approach to making sense of the cosmos beyond event horizons. Mann's lecture is an important moment with regard to what is in and out of sight, and the ways in which love might not resolve in the evolutionary ways that Mann understands. Mann cannot think beyond certain functionalities. Having theorised love as a basic behaviouristic survival instinct, Mann reveals he has insufficiently attended to love as a theoretically rich line of inquiry in its own right. Love is beyond Mann's questions and his horizon; he misunderstands what he has discovered about knowledge and being, and "allows the possibility of no other reality-revealing horizon" (Young, 2002, p. 29).

If Mann allows for the possibility that love transcends time and space, he discovers new questions. What might happen then if children and teachers question the whats and hows and whys of the reality-revealing horizon of behaviourism? Perhaps their questions would make these star charts seem somehow strange ... to wonder how those beautiful stars in the sky, that offer up ideas of unknowable life and death, that hint at dimensions of time and gravity beyond sight, became the crude instrument of a community's love for enframing the behaviour of children. I wonder whether then this love might also be revealed for its very Modern tendencies, and then put aside to grow dust, replaced with a different kind of less anxious, more questioning, more dimensional, more essential, love.

As an early childhood teacher and teacher educator in Aotearoa New Zealand, for me it's not just love that is of interest here, but the way in which love is thought differently through the partnership established in the signing of the aforementioned treaty, which consists of two treaties: the Treaty of Waitangi and te Titiri o Waitangi, two versions of an agreement in two languages with the purpose of coming together in partnership.

One place to look for that partnership is in the early childhood curriculum. It is perhaps getting

closer to the source of love. In Aotearoa New Zealand's early childhood curriculum *Te Whāriki* (Ministry of Education, 2017), love is a secondary concept to *aroha*. *Aroha* is explained as love, compassion, empathy and affection (p. 66). *Aroha* is a key curriculum concept with regard to the child's learning dispositions, relationship to *Papatūānuku* (typically explained as the Earth mother), and relationships with peers. The curriculum can be seen then as guiding *mahi aroha*, practices through which mana is recognised, protected, and enhanced (Cram, 2021), and invites thinking about the kind of measuring that compels Heidegger and Camus, and at the same time invites a concern for any sciences that anxiously attempt to fix education and childhood through blinkered approaches to measurement. Take for example this star chart phenomenon.

The managerial star chart is emblematic of events that have occurred in early childhood education over the two decades either side of the turn of the millennium and that obscure anxieties with regard to the enumeration of the child in ways that trouble this heart. When I started out teaching in early childhood education many years ago, the early childhood education sector had only just appeared on the educational radar of the Cold War. It was largely free to do whatever it wished with regard to providing for the care and education of children, and many children were not likely to spend much more than 20 hours a week in an early childhood centre.

Travelling through time, to early childhood education, here in Aotearoa New Zealand now, we have this seemingly paradoxical situation in which the Government maintains that early childhood education is not a compulsory educational stage, but at the same time compels parents to send their children to early childhood education centres at increasingly younger ages, for increasing hours in the week.

I am concerned with what is overlooked, discarded, marginalised, and exploited in this brave new world of early childhood education. I am particularly concerned with the incessant and absurd production of star charts and other tools to measure the young child's educational progress. For instance, we are currently, in Aotearoa New Zealand, being asked to implement a host of new "progress tools" to amplify the attention to evidence of each child's learning and development. We must measure the children more.

I read in Heidegger, Camus, and *Interstellar* a challenge to education systems obsessed with the metric production of educational quantities. The enumeration of each child, and of all children, educationally, appears to be an absurd obsession, fixated with producing numbers and rarely, in Heidegger's terms, paying heed to those productions, nor to the nature of number (Heidegger, 1971, p. 224). I am wondering whether a fixation of enumerating the child might be challenged not just through a turn to Heidegger but also a turn to the kind of hard science fiction that questions the truths of the educational sciences, and that opens up questions concerning events, horizons, education and love.

A love-oriented curriculum can be understood in different ways.

Of course, there's the possibility that love becomes some kind of truth, or a prescribed lesson, and something to assess. Perhaps the main caution here is to think of love as a phenomenon worth more study. To study love is not to determine its finality. The point is not to harass love until it's a thing that can be put to work for some agenda, but to dwell poetically in love (Heidegger, 1971).

Perhaps in dwelling poetically in the study of love there is some recognition of the very tendency to turn love into a potion for “gain and success” (Heidegger, 1971, p. 213). In other words, an education reform movement that seeks to install love into curriculum as a subject area, or into pedagogy as a teaching tool, could end up looking and feeling just as absurd as every other instrumental and technical curriculum subject and pedagogy, a reform that might rarely extend beyond our line of sight.

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